

1 **Micro(nano)plastics in the total environment – a holistic review**

2 Katarzyna Jaszczyszyn ^{a, b, *}, Edyta Kiedrzyńska ^{a, c, *}, Dominika Matuszewska ^{a, c, d}, Jinkai Xue ^e,
3 Marcin Kiedrzyński ^f

4 ^a European Regional Centre for Ecohydrology of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Tylina 3, 90-364 Lodz, Poland

5 ^b Poznan University of Technology, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Energy, Institute of Environmental
6 Engineering and Building Installations, Berdychowo 4, 60-965 Poznan, Poland

7 ^c University of Lodz, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, UNESCO Chair on Ecohydrology and Applied
8 Ecology, Banacha 12/16, 90-237 Lodz, Poland

9 ^d University of Lodz, Doctoral School of Extract and Natural Sciences, Jana Matejki 21/23, 90-237 Lodz, Poland

10 ^e Cold-Region Water Resource Recovery Laboratory (CRWRRL), Environmental Systems Engineering, Faculty of
11 Engineering & Applied Science, University of Regina, 3737 Wascana Parkway, Regina, SK S4S 0A2, Canada.

12 ^f University of Lodz, Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, Department of Biogeography, Paleoecology and
13 Nature Conservation, Banacha 1/3, 90-237 Lodz, Poland

14

15 *Corresponding authors:

16 k.jaszczyszyn@erce.unesco.lodz.pl; katarzyna.jaszczyszyn@put.poznan.pl

17 e.kiedrznaska@erce.unesco.lodz.pl

18 ORCID numbers: K.J.: 0000-0003-3814-0183; E.K.:0000-0003-0649-4438; D.M.:0000-0002-3586-8155; JX: 0000-

19 0002-8824-1495; M.K.: 0000-0002-1751-9357

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21

22 **Abstract**

23 Microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs) in the environment pose a significant challenge. They
24 can accumulate at high levels in soil, air, water, sediments, and living organisms. Although long-
25 term exposure to MPs can harm all living organisms, including humans, the transport, fate, and
26 impacts of global micro(nano)plastic pollution remain poorly understood. This review provides
27 a holistic perspective on the production, degradation, accumulation and fate of plastic particles
28 in the total environment and sheds light on their complex interactions within various
29 environmental matrices. The review provides an overview of global plastic production and
30 recycling rates. It goes on to address the degradation and classification of plastic debris and
31 presents methodologies for detecting plastic particles in environmental samples. It also examines
32 the impact of plastic particles on living organisms, including humans. Finally, the review highlights
33 existing regulatory frameworks relating to industrial production, as well as the analysis and
34 detection of plastics in consumer products and environmental samples. By emphasizing the key
35 factors that influence the transfer and transformation of plastic residues, this paper provides
36 insights for future research and policy development and presents innovative solutions,
37 underscoring the urgent need for a coordinated global response to manage plastic pollution.

38 **Keywords:** microplastic particles, nanoplastics, transfer into environmental matrices,
39 bioaccumulation, toxicity, law regulations

40

41

- 42 **Abbreviations:**
- 43 ABS: acrylonitrile butadiene styrene terpolymer
- 44 d.m.: dry matter content
- 45 DWTPs: drinking water treatment plant
- 46 EPS: expanded polystyrene
- 47 EVOH EVAL: ethylene vinyl alcohol copolymer
- 48 FTIR: Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy
- 49 HD-PE/LD-PE: high- and low-density polyethylene
- 50 MPs: microplastics
- 51 NBS: nature-based solutions
- 52 NPs: nanoplastics
- 53 MNPs: Micro(nano)plastics
- 54 PA: polyamide/nylon
- 55 PC: polycarbonate
- 56 PE: polyethylene
- 57 PES: polyester
- 58 PEVA/EVA: (poly)ethylene vinyl acetate copolymers
- 59 PET: polyethylene terephthalate
- 60 PMA: polyethyl acrylate
- 61 PMMA: polymethyl methacrylate
- 62 POPs: persistent organic pollutants
- 63 PP: polypropylene
- 64 PS: polystyrene
- 65 PTFE: polytetrafluoroethylene (Teflon)
- 66 PUR: polyurethane
- 67 PVA: polyvinyl alcohol
- 68 PVC: poly(vinyl chloride)
- 69 SBR: styrene-butadiene rubber
- 70 WWTPs: wastewater treatment plants
- 71

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117 **1. Introduction**

118 Plastic products are indispensable in the modern society. As a result of their widespread use,
119 plastic residues are found almost everywhere in the environment: in the ocean (Bergmann et al.,
120 2015; Cózar et al., 2015), in fresh water reservoirs (Andrade et al., 2019; Połec et al., 2018), in
121 wastewater and sediments (Blair et al., 2019; Castañeda et al., 2014; Magni et al., 2019), in the
122 air (Abbasi et al., 2019; Xie et al., 2022) and even in living organisms i.e. in human blood (Leslie et
123 al., 2022) or organs (Horvatits et al., 2022; Jenner, Rotchell, et al., 2022), and in animal tissues
124 (Kögel et al., 2023; Su et al., 2019). This is hence a global issue, as plastic particles can have
125 a negative impact on both the environment and health of living organisms, including humans.

126 Despite steady progress in analytical capabilities and sample preparation methods, our
127 holistic understanding of global plastic pollution and the factors influencing the spread of plastics
128 remains relatively poor. Few research reports have taken a comprehensive approach to
129 examining plastic pollution and plastic circulation within larger areas, e.g. a river catchment area
130 or an ecosystem. Moreover, due to the heterogeneity in sampling and sample preparation and
131 lack of legal regulations dedicated to different matrices, it is difficult to compare their findings.
132 Furthermore, environmental samples are often collected instantaneously, which may decrease
133 the repeatability of the research results, plastic residues in the natural environment will undergo
134 degradation and aging processes (Romera-Castillo et al., 2022). Plastics are also modified during
135 production to strengthen them or, for example, improve their anti-corrosion properties; as such,
136 their residues may serve as a vector of pollution, e.g. heavy metals or other persistent organic
137 pollutants POPs (e.g. synthetic dyes, UV stabilizers, bacteriostatic or anti-corrosion additives)
138 (Gkika et al., 2023). Therefore, there is a constant need to monitor the flow of plastic throughout
139 the entire environment and the food chain. However, this might be impossible due to tremendous
140 factors that influence the circulation of plastic residues in the environment.

141 This comprehensive review aims to highlight the problem of plastic residues, particularly
142 microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs), present throughout the atmosphere, hydrosphere,
143 lithosphere and anthroposphere, and examine their interactions with each other. It provides
144 a holistic view of the occurrence of plastic particles, their sources and their environmental fate.
145 Additionally, some selected and most important factors influencing the transfer of plastic residues
146 in the environment will be presented.

147 **2. Plastics - global production and consumption vs. waste and recycling rate**

148 The term *plastics* encompasses a wide range of polymers that form an indispensable part
149 of modern life. Although the production of synthetic polymers began at the end of the 19th
150 century, they became popular in the mid-20th century (Bergmann et al., 2015; Geyer, 2020), and
151 it is estimated that half of all plastics ever produced were made in the last two decades (OECD,
152 2018). Plastics are valued for their strength-to-weight ratio and resistance to chemical, biological
153 and physical degradation (OECD, 2018). Due to their low density, durability, excellent barrier

154 properties and relatively low cost (Geyer et al., 2017; WHO, 2022), they have found a very wide
155 range of applications ranging from clothing, housing and construction materials to storage,
156 packaging and fluid transportation (Cronin et al., 2022; Subramanian, 2011), medical applications
157 (Czuba, 2014), and agriculture, e.g. pond liners, irrigation pipes, plastic-coated seeds and mulch
158 film (UNEP, 2022b). Plastics can also be used to strengthen materials to improve their durability
159 and reduce production costs, and these have become a substitute for many conventional
160 materials, e.g. the cement, glass, metal, wood or paper used in construction (Cronin et al., 2022;
161 Geyer et al., 2017; OECD, 2018).

162 Structurally, plastics include a wide group of synthetic polymers prepared by
163 polymerization or polycondensation from coal, alcohol, natural gas or petroleum (Geyer, 2020;
164 Subramanian, 2011). Many different types of polymers are used to produce commercial products,
165 and hence the polymers present in the environment can be very diverse, with different chemical
166 and mechanical properties (Bergmann et al., 2015; Geyer et al., 2017). Plastics can be divided into
167 several groups based on polymer type (Geyer, 2020; M. K. Singh et al., 2023) including:
168 polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE), high- and low-density polyethylene (HDPE, LDPE),
169 polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS) and expanded polystyrene (EPS),
170 poly(vinylchloride) (PVC), polyurethane (PUR), polyamide/nylon (PA), polycarbonate (PC) and
171 other fossil-based thermoplastics, recycled plastics and bio-based/ bio-attributed plastics.
172 Another category is polyethylene vinyl acetate copolymers (PEVA), which are a type of non-
173 chlorinated vinyl often used as a safer alternative to PVC, as they are considered less toxic and
174 more environmentally friendly. Unlike PVC, PEVA does not release harmful chlorine-based
175 chemicals when it breaks down.

176 The largest global plastic producer is Asia, which is responsible for over half of global
177 production. China alone reached about one third of global plastic production in 2021 (Ng et al.,
178 2023; OECD, 2022; Plastics Europe, 2022). The second largest producer is North America
179 (including the USA, Canada and Mexico) with a share of 18% of world production, followed by
180 Europe (13%; 57.2 Mt), Middle East and Africa (8%) and Latin America (4%) (Plastics Europe,
181 2022). The European countries with the highest production were Germany, with over 23% of
182 European plastic production, followed by Italy and France, with 14.3 and 9.4%, respectively.
183 Poland, Spain and the United Kingdom had similar annual production in the European market, of
184 around 7% (Plastics Europe, 2022; Statistics Poland, 2023). The two largest world plastics markets
185 in 2021 were packaging (44%) and building & construction (18%) (see Figure 1A) (Plastics Europe,
186 2022).

187 Global plastic production is expected to continue to increase in the coming decades,
188 despite the turbulence on the global market during the Covid-19 pandemic: in 2021 a 4% increase
189 to over 390 million tons in worldwide production was reported (OECD, 2022; Plastics Europe,
190 2022). It is projected that plastic production continue to rise to reach over 1.2 billion metric tons
191 by 2060 (OECD, 2022).

192 The major sectors consuming plastics, i.e. packaging, non-packaging household products,
 193 construction and automotive, together represent approximately 75% of total consumption (see
 194 Figure 1A) (Plastics Europe, 2022). Among them, packaging is the main source of plastic
 195 consumption, accounting for 39.1% in Europe and 44% globally (this data does not include
 196 industrial packaging) (Plastics Europe, 2022).

197 The rapid growth of plastic use is accompanied by the problem of their proper
 198 management and emission into the natural environment. Due to improper management,
 199 a significant part (over 20%) of plastic waste ends up in uncontrolled landfills or is burned in the
 200 open, leading to leakage into the environment (OECD, 2022). Unfortunately, most plastic waste
 201 currently ends up in landfills (Plastics Europe, 2022), and it is also predicted that by 2060, almost
 202 half of all plastic waste will still go to landfill, and less than a fifth will be recycled (OECD, 2022).

203
 204 **Figure 1.** The global and European plastics distribution: (A) Share by application and (B) Production by
 205 polymer type (*Others include fossil-based thermosets and thermoplastics; Bioplastics: bio-based/
 206 bio-attributed plastics; data based on: (Plastics Europe, 2022, 2024))

207 Worldwide, the most commonly used polymer is PE, which makes up 26.2% of global
 208 consumption. It is utilized in various applications, including packaging, construction, automotive,
 209 agriculture, household items, sports equipment, and electronics. The second most prevalent
 210 polymer is PP (19%) (Plastics Europe, 2024). In 2023, polyolefins (i.e. PP and PE) constituted of
 211 37.1% of the demand of European plastics (see Figure 1B), representing a decline of 3.5%
 212 compared to 2021 (Plastics Europe, 2022, 2024; M. K. Singh et al., 2023). For comparison, in
 213 Poland, polyolefins accounted for about 43% of the total production in 2022 (Statistics Poland,
 214 2024), with an increase of 3.5% compared to 2021.

215 According to statistics, in 2021, plastic recycling accounted for about 8.3% of global
 216 production, while in the European market this rate was 10%. In 2023, there was a slight increase
 217 in global recycling, reaching 8.7%, while in Europe this rate increased to 19% (Plastics Europe,
 218 2022, 2023, 2024).

219 The United Nations has a long-term vision to end global plastic pollution. The ‘United
 220 Nations Plastics Initiative’ aims to achieve several strategic goals that enable a radical market
 221 transformation towards a resource-efficient circular economy of plastics: reducing the size of the
 222 problem by eliminating and replacing some plastics with recycled ones, designing for and ensuring
 223 circularity, and implementing appropriate management of waste that cannot be reused or
 224 recycled (UNEP, 2022b).

225 As plastics can persist in the environment for a very long time (Cronin et al., 2022; Geyer,
 226 2020; Geyer et al., 2017) and can bioaccumulate in plants and living organisms, it is extremely
 227 important to achieve circularity for plastics. It is also important to note that many include various
 228 compounds added during production to strengthen the material (Bergmann et al., 2015), which
 229 can be released into the environment as the plastics degrade or age (Paluselli et al., 2019; Turner
 230 et al., 2020).

231 3. Degradation and classification of plastic materials

232 Plastic waste is subject to various aging processes (Hüffer et al., 2018) resulting in the
 233 leaching of dissolved organic compounds, typically plastic oligomers and various compounds
 234 added in the production of plastics (Romera-Castillo et al., 2022). It should be mentioned that
 235 aged MPs have higher sorption capacities for micropollutants than virgin MPs (Bao et al., 2022).
 236 As such, the morphology of parent particles will change with aging (Hüffer et al., 2018).

237
 238 **Figure 2.** Classification and characteristics of plastic particles, and plastic degradation in response to
 239 environmental factors

240 All these processes lead to the fragmentation and the physical, chemical and biological
241 degradation of plastics. Such degradation can generally follow five different mechanisms, possibly
242 ending in complete mineralization: biodegradation by microorganisms, photo degradation,
243 usually by UV light (L. Liu et al., 2022), thermal degradation (Hernandez et al., 2023), chemical
244 degradation (oxidation or hydrolysis) and mechanical degradation (Sutkar et al., 2023) (see Figure
245 2). Polymer degradation is influenced by various factors, which can be broadly divided into
246 polymer properties and weathering characteristics (Glaser, 2019). The former include surface
247 area, molecular weight, bond types, branching, stereochemistry flexibility, crystallinity, additives,
248 hydrophobic and hydrophilic interactions, morphology, e.g. shape and size (Ahmed et al., 2018;
249 Mierzwa-Hersztek et al., 2019). The latter can be divided into biotic (contributing to
250 biodegradation) and abiotic factors (Hüffer et al., 2018). Biotic factors include hydrophobicity,
251 extracellular enzymes specificity, nutrients, biosurfactants, algal and fungal degradation (L. Liu et
252 al., 2022; Mohanan et al., 2020), with biodeterioration, biofragmentation, assimilation and
253 mineralization all playing roles in the biodegradation of synthetic plastics (Y. He et al., 2024).
254 Abiotic factors include various environmental factors such as sunlight, oxidation, pH, salinity,
255 humidity and temperature which cause such phenomena as weathering and leaching (Mohanan
256 et al., 2020).

257 All of the above factors will affect the aging and decay of plastics, and their fragmentation
258 into smaller particles. However, it should be remembered that these processes will occur in the
259 environment to varying degrees depending on the material. The plastics present in the
260 environment are typically only fragments: particles and remains of man-made materials that
261 come in various sizes, shapes, and colors (see Figure 2). Such remnants are most often classified
262 based on their size (longest dimension: diameter or length) with four groups being recognised:
263 macroplastics, mesoplastics, MPs and NPs. However, the definition of these groups varies. For
264 example, macroplastics are particles with the largest dimension >10 mm or >25mm, mesoplastics
265 range from 1 to 10 mm or 5-25mm, MPs from 1 to 1000 μm (or to 5000 μm), and NPs below 1
266 micron (Allen et al., 2022; Bermúdez & Swarzenski, 2021). The 2020 Technical Report of the
267 International Organization for Standardization ISO/TR 21960:2020 (ISO, 2020) classified plastic
268 particles onto three main groups: macroplastics with any dimension >5 mm, large MPs between
269 1 and 5 mm, microplastics from 1 to 1000 μm , and nanoplastics smaller than 1 μm . In contrast,
270 the United Nations Environment Programme document number UNEP/PP/INC.1/7 defines
271 nanoplastics as a subset of microplastics, usually with a size below 100 nm (UNEP, 2022b).
272 Similarly, Frias and Nash define microplastics as any synthetic solid particles or polymer matrix
273 between 1 μm and 5 mm in size, of regular or irregular shape, of primary or secondary origin,
274 which are insoluble in water (Frias & Nash, 2019).

275 Many researchers adopt a more general classification into three groups, with
276 macroplastics being particles larger than 5 mm, microplastics between 1 μm and 5 mm, and
277 nanoplastics below 1 micron (AMAP, 2021; V. K. Sharma et al., 2023). Interestingly, an additional

278 division of plastic particles according to categories already used in plankton research has recently
279 been proposed by Bermúdez and Swarzenski (Bermúdez & Swarzenski, 2021), viz. femto-size
280 (0.02–0.2 μm), pico-size (0.2–2 μm), nano-size (2–20 μm), micro-size (20–200 μm), meso-sized
281 (200–2000 μm), macro-size plastics (0.2–20 cm) and mega-size plastics (20–200 cm).

282 In addition to the most commonly-used division based on particle size, MPs can also be
283 classified based on their origin, i.e. primary and secondary, physico-chemical properties,
284 strengthening additives used and their morphology, i.e. color, shape (Rosal, 2021). Although there
285 is no unified protocol for identifying plastic particles, they are generally characterized by at least
286 polymer type, size, color and shape (Prata et al., 2024).

287 Plastic particles will occur in the environment in various forms and at various degradation
288 and fragmentation stages, and their presence will result in progressive disintegration into smaller
289 and smaller particles, thus increasing the scope of their transfer to living organisms. Therefore, it
290 is important to continually improve and simplify the methods of detecting plastic particles and, if
291 possible, removing them from the environment, thus reducing the number of uncontrolled
292 discharges or waste landfills. Therefore, it is important to facilitate greater segregation, retention
293 at source and reuse of plastics, and time strive to create legal regulations limiting the transfer of
294 plastic particles into the environment, for example in sewage.

295 **4. Methods for the preparation and analysis of plastic particles in environmental samples**

296 Due to the complexity of environmental matrices, monitoring microplastics in the
297 environment is difficult (Al-Azzawi et al., 2020). The collected samples should be properly
298 prepared in advance to remove organic and mineral matter that may interfere with the analysis.
299 Due to the great variations in environmental matrices, standardizing the methods of sample
300 preparation is difficult, and this presents the greatest challenge in MNPs collection and analysis
301 (Prata et al., 2024). Analyses also face challenges related to contamination control, lack of
302 specialized laboratory equipment, and the difficulty in identifying MNPs from other particles.
303 Many researchers also rely on previous reports while optimizing the methodologies of MNPs
304 collection, preparation, and analyses. Figure 3 summarizes the subsequent steps of working with
305 environmental samples, including methods for preparing and analyzing plastic particles.

306
307 **Figure 3.** Methods of preparation and analysis of MNPs particles in environmental tests

308 **4.1. Laboratory guidelines and recommendations for analysis of MNPs**

309 In 2015, the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) issued
310 recommendations for quantifying synthetic particles in marine waters and sediments (Mausra &
311 Foster, 2015). They indicate general methodological guidelines for sample preparation
312 (apparatus, transfer of sieved solids) by preparing samples for analysis, including wet peroxide
313 oxidation (for removing organic matter) and density separation (for removing mineral matter), as
314 well as general rules for microscopic and gravimetric analyses. Although these have formed the
315 basis of various studies, these general assumptions have since been improved and additionally
316 extended to include other matrices such as freshwater and sediments (Campanale et al., 2020;
317 Rubirola et al., 2019; Schrank, Möller, et al., 2022), wastewater and sludge (Al-Azzawi et al., 2020;
318 Raju et al., 2020), soil (Arenas-Lago et al., 2022; Athulya et al., 2024; Scopetani et al., 2020), air
319 (Shao et al., 2022), as well as plant, animal (Fu et al., 2020; Rivoira et al., 2020; Valsesia et al.,
320 2021) and human tissues (S. Wang et al., 2023).

321 Some general principles of microplastic analysis, from sampling and preparation to
322 detection methods, were also published in May 2021 by the German Federal Institute of Material
323 Research (Braun, 2021).

324 In addition, the principles to be followed when analyzing MPs in various environmental
325 matrices are summarised in the latest ISO document No. 24187:2023(E), published in September
326 2023 (ISO, 2023). It emphasises appropriate sample collection, sample preparation, i.e. extraction

327 of MPs from a given matrix, and detection using an appropriate technique. It recommends
328 following good practice for collecting liquid or solid samples based on the previous ISO series,
329 indicating that the lower expected particle content requires greater sample volume to test both
330 the mass and number of particles. In addition, it is also required to work in plastic-free or low-
331 plastic conditions at each stage and to avoid contamination, including cross-contamination, i.e.
332 working with containers made of glass, ceramics, or metal. All more detailed guidelines are
333 included in ISO: 24187:2023(E) (ISO, 2023).

334 **4.2. Sample preparation**

335 Depending on the environmental matrix being analyzed, appropriate sample preparation
336 methods are selected (Braun, 2021). MPs extraction most often includes density separation and
337 organic digestion method, preceded by filtration in the case of liquid samples (see Figure 3).
338 Mineral matter is typically removed using salt solutions with a density higher than the density of
339 the polymers, such as sodium chloride NaCl, zinc chloride ZnCl₂ or sodium iodide NaI solutions
340 (Schrank, Möller, et al., 2022). Particles of the most commonly used plastics can, therefore, be
341 separated from higher-density matrices by flotation with high-density saturated salt solutions
342 (Löder & Gerdts, 2015). Some researchers also propose an easy and inexpensive extraction
343 method using olive oil as an alternative to density separation methods (Scopetani et al., 2020).
344 The authors indicate that this method can be applied to MPs of size 0.2 – 5 mm if a bench-top
345 Fourier transform infrared microscopy (FTIR) is used for the identification, and down to 5 µm for
346 a microscope-FTIR instrument. Typically, the decaying organic matter contained in samples, such
347 as algae and bacteria, is digested by catalytic oxidation using strong oxidants such as hydrogen
348 peroxide H₂O₂ or the Fenton reagent (Alavian Petroody et al., 2020). However, acid/alkaline
349 treatment with HCl, HNO₃, NaOH or enzymatic degradation (e.g. lipase, amylase, proteinase,
350 chitinase, cellulase) is also used (Parashar & Hait, 2023). However, it needs to be noted that some
351 sample purification protocols may lead to weight loss in the polymers tested (Schrank, Möller, et
352 al., 2022).

353 **4.3. Methods of analysis**

354 Various detection methods based on different measurement principles are available for
355 the analysis of MNPs (see Figure 3). In general, three different detection approaches can be
356 mentioned: visual, spectroscopic and thermoanalytical methods (Arenas-Lago et al., 2022). Of
357 these, the visual methods are the simplest, as well as the *hot needle test*. This also includes
358 analyses based on an optical microscope, stereoscopic microscope or scanning electron
359 microscopy (SEM). These methods are quick to perform and usually do not require the use of
360 expensive equipment. On the other hand, they are (partially) limited in terms of the analytical
361 accuracy of polymer particles, since they are subjective and depend on the knowledge of the
362 researcher (Arenas-Lago et al., 2022).

363 Spectroscopic detection methods allow for quantitative and qualitative analysis. They
364 allow the determination of polymer type by comparing the chemical structures of the studied
365 polymers against reference spectra (ISO, 2023). They also allow the number, size distribution and
366 shape of MPs particles to be determined (Braun, 2021). The employed methods rely on vibrational
367 spectroscopy techniques, including those at the microscopic level, while considering different
368 measurement systems. Currently, the most commonly used methods for MPs identification and
369 characterization are Fourier transform infrared spectrometry (FTIR), attenuated total reflection
370 Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy (Arenas-Lago et al.,
371 2022). Other methods include focal plane array detector FTIR (FPA-FTIR), quantum cascade laser
372 induced infrared spectroscopy (QCL-IR) or near or short-wave infrared spectroscopy (NIR, SWIR)
373 (ISO, 2023).

374 In thermoanalytical/chemical methods, the sample is pyrolyzed under neutral conditions,
375 and the specific decomposition products of individual polymers are detected (ISO, 2023). The
376 resulting volatile pyrolysis products are closely associated with the nature of the polymer and can
377 be used to assess the chemical composition of the microplastic particles (Löder & Gerds, 2015).
378 Pyrolysis systems are usually combined with gas chromatography, preferably with mass
379 spectrometry detection (Py-GC/MS system), as well as thermal extraction desorption
380 chromatography (TED-GC/MS), thermogravimetric analysis mass spectrometry (TGA-MS)
381 (Arenas-Lago et al., 2022).

382 Each of the aforementioned methods facilitates the analysis of plastic particles, including
383 both MPs and NPs. The choice of an appropriate MNPs analysis method depends on the specific
384 goals of the research project and the requirements for quantitative and/or qualitative detection
385 (Prata et al., 2024). Analytical techniques for MNPs analysis can be selected based on particle size.
386 ATR-FTIR is advised for analyzing particles larger than 500 μm , while light microscopy is suitable
387 for particles $>10 \mu\text{m}$. FTIR and μFTIR can be used for small particles up to 1 μm , and Raman is
388 effective for particles in the range of 0.1 to 1 μm . SEM is appropriate for particles up to 1 μm and
389 photothermal-induced resonance (also known as AFM-IR atomic force microscopy), can detect
390 particles down to 100 nm (B. Singh & Kumar, 2024).

391 The analysis of NPs presents unique challenges because of their small size and the
392 necessity for highly sensitive detection methods that can provide reliable information on their
393 presence, characteristics, and potential ecotoxicological impacts. Some of the best methods
394 highlighted in the literature for the analysis of NPs in environmental samples include
395 chromatographic methods such as Py-GC/MS and TED-GC/MS. Among the spectroscopic
396 techniques, Raman spectroscopy is the most commonly mentioned (Ivleva, 2021).

397 **5. Plastic particles in different environmental matrices**

398 MNPs enter the natural environment through various channels such as through direct
399 sewage discharge, wastewater networks, dry and wet deposition or surface runoff, and

400 fragmentation of plastic waste that has entered the environment (see Figure 4). Each of the
401 subsystems (land as the lithosphere, water as the hydrosphere, living beings as the biosphere and
402 air as the atmosphere) are subject to constant change and interact directly or indirectly.

403 MNP pose significant physical and toxicological risks for living organisms and are poorly
404 defined from an analytical point of view and their measurement in the environment remains
405 a challenge. Moreover, their increasingly widespread presence raises concerns for both human
406 health and ecosystems. The nature of the interactions occurring in a natural system may influence
407 the release of plastic particles into environmental components. The chemical or physical impact
408 of MPs may cause serious changes in the environment, which may result in contamination of
409 water reservoirs and soil. Long-term exposure to MPs and NPs may lead to the degeneration of
410 physical, neurological, and endocrine systems (Leso et al., 2023). Despite much research, and
411 improved sample preparation methods, little is still known about global MP pollution, the
412 circulation of MPs in the environment, or the factors influencing their spread. Furthermore, there
413 is no comprehensive overview connecting the global presence of MPs and NPs with the
414 surrounding environment of humans and other living organisms.

415 The following section will highlight the individual environmental components where MNPs
416 have been detected (see Figure 4), as well as their potential sources or transfer routes, factors
417 influencing their accumulation, transport or degradation, and their impact on living organisms
418 and environmental implications (see Table 1). This comprehensive review is intended to raise
419 awareness of future threats to soil and water and to living organisms.

420
421 **Figure 4.** Transfer of MPs to the environment and their circulation throughout the total environment

Table 1. Key factors influencing the abundance, sources, characteristics, fate, and impact of MNPs across environmental matrices

	Key factors influencing MNPs abundance	Occurrence	Main sources	Characteristics	Fate	Impact	
Air	climatic conditions, i.e. wind speed and direction, precipitation types and intensities, temperature, and their interactions with neighboring environments and the levels of human activity	street dust, indoor and outdoor air, clouds, and precipitation (snow, rain)	human activity - everyday life (i.e. clothing, textiles, transportation), industrial emission	various sizes and colors; mostly fiber-shaped in indoor and outdoor air and dust; fragments and fibers in snow; rubber fragments in wet deposition	biotic and abiotic degradation and aging affecting POPs adsorption ability; fragmentation into smaller particles; transport to remote areas; sedimentation	inhalation of airborne MNPs, causing inflammation and oxidative stress; POPs transfer; contribute to climate change as condensation nuclei in clouds	
Water and sediments	Marine water	rainfall patterns, seasonal changes, geography, land use, local pollution sources; hydrodynamic conditions; industrial pollution; urban and agricultural runoff	coastal zones, open water of seas and oceans at various depths, ocean gyres, remote regions in Arctic and Antarctic	wastewater discharge, marine activities (fishing, shipping), tourism; atmospheric deposition; land-based runoff; plastic waste - improper disposal and littering	various sizes (including larger fragments) and colors; dominant shapes - fragments, fibers, and beads; predominant polymers PE, PP, PS	biotic and abiotic degradation and aging affecting POPs adsorption ability; fragmentation into smaller particles; transport to remote areas; sedimentation	ingestion of food-like particles by aquatic organisms, entanglement; bioaccumulation and trophic transfer of POPs and pathogens linked to MNPs; ecosystem disruption
	Freshwater	as above	lakes and rivers at different water depths, sediments	urban runoff (tire wear, plastic litter); WWTPs effluents; industrial discharge; agricultural runoff (fertilizers, mulch films); atmospheric deposition; recreation	various sizes and colors; dominant shapes - fragments, fibers, and films; main polymers PE, PP, PS and PVC	as above	as above
	Drinking water	insufficient water source protection, disordered water management; pipe material; packaging methods, washing, transport and storage system used	groundwater, tap water, bottled water, beverages	source water pollution (industrial discharges, urban runoff, agriculture); plastic packaging; aging plastic pipes in distribution system	various sizes (typically smaller particles and NPs) and colors; dominant shape fibers; polymer types PE, PP, PET, PES, PTFE	as above	ingestion by humans, bioaccumulation and trophic transfer of harmful pollutants and pathogens associated with MNPs

Wastewater and sludge	spatial and temporal variations, human activity intensity, industrialization; inadequate wastewater management, e.g. insufficient WWTP capacity; applied wastewater pre-treatment and treatment systems	each treatment step varies significantly by season, geography, and human activity	domestic wastewater (laundry, personal care products), storm overflows, urban runoff (tire wear abrasion, plastic packaging, and products breakdown), industrial wastewater (i.e. textile production, washing systems)	various sizes, shapes, and polymer types; dominant subtype in urban wastewater - fibers (textiles i.e. PES, PA); MNPs behavior in WWT systems influenced by physicochemical properties (density, particle size, and hydrophobicity)	accumulation in sludge; fragmentation into smaller particles; despite high WWT efficiency - MNPs release with effluents; removal effectiveness varying by treatment technology	destabilization of WWT processes, affecting operational stability; POPs transport; constant environmental discharge; ingestion of food-like particles by aquatic organisms; bioaccumulation and biomagnification; soil contamination by sludge used for agriculture
Soil	improper wastewater and waste management; type and intensity of land use; proximity to urban areas; agricultural practices such as plowing influencing MNPs spread	MNPs found in various soil types, mainly in agricultural lands using sewage sludge as fertilizer	improper waste disposal and littering; atmospheric deposition; runoff; agricultural use of sewage sludge as fertilizer and plastic mulch	various sizes, shapes, and polymer types	penetration into deeper soil layers; fragmentation into smaller fragments; long-term soil persistence	deep soil penetration; groundwater pollution risk; accumulation and bioavailability affecting plant uptake; disruption of microbial communities crucial for nutrient cycling

424 **5.1. Air**

425 Although most studies on the presence of MNPs in the environment focus on aquatic matrices,
426 MNPs have also been found in the atmosphere: in clouds (Y. Wang et al., 2023), street dust
427 (Abbasi et al., 2019; P. Liu et al., 2022), in indoor and outdoor urban air (Nematollahi et al., 2022;
428 Perera et al., 2022), or atmospheric precipitation, including snow (Lasota et al., 2023), as well as
429 in distant and untouched environments such as national parks (Ohno & Iizuka, 2023) or Arctic (Y.
430 Zhang et al., 2023) and Antarctic areas (Aves et al., 2022; Cunningham et al., 2022) (see Table S1).

431 The occurrence and abundance of airborne MPs and NPs depends primarily on climatic
432 conditions such as wind speed and direction, intensity and type of precipitation, and temperature
433 (Cunningham et al., 2022). Thus, it depends on interactions and connections with neighboring
434 environments and the intensity of human activity.

435 The main source of MNPs in the atmosphere is human activity (Jenner, Sadofsky, et al.,
436 2022), contributing to both the type and quantity of airborne MNPs. The concentrations are
437 higher indoors than outdoors (Perera et al., 2022). Studies of dust settled in office rooms, schools
438 and apartments show that the amount of microplastic collected in individual locations on
439 weekdays exceeded the amount detected on weekends, with significantly higher amounts noted
440 in offices than in homes (Bahrina et al., 2020). Similar results were found by Nematollahi et al.,
441 who studied microplastic occurrence in settled indoor dust in schools (Nematollahi et al., 2022).
442 The highest abundance of MPs was found in areas characterized by high population density, heavy
443 road traffic and the presence of industrial units and workshops. Therefore, the type of activity
444 and the number of occupants in a given space directly affect the indoor amounts of microplastics.

445 A significant share of MPs is produced locally through everyday life, i.e. the use of plastic
446 products (clothes, textiles, toys, accessories) (Perera et al., 2022) and industrial production
447 (Jenner, Sadofsky, et al., 2022). This causes the release of MNPs, which settle in indoor dust or
448 become airborne particles. Greater population density and greater industrial activity generate
449 greater amounts of airborne MPs (Bahrina et al., 2020; Nematollahi et al., 2022). In high-density
450 areas, the greatest outdoor MPs abundance is observed near industrial zones, followed by urban
451 and inland locations (P. Liu et al., 2022). Research conducted in Beijing showed that a significant
452 amount of PP particles were detected in the central part of the city, where there are numerous
453 service industries producing a large number of packaging products (P. Liu et al., 2022). PA particles
454 in the form of fibers were detected in large quantities in the southern part of the city,
455 characterised by high population density and a textile industry.

456 The majority of airborne pollutants are fiber-shaped, observed not only in urban
457 environments (Bahrina et al., 2020; P. Liu et al., 2022; Nematollahi et al., 2022) but also across
458 long-distance transport (Chen et al., 2023) or unpopulated areas (Aves et al., 2022; Cunningham
459 et al., 2022; Y. Zhang, Gao, et al., 2021). On the other hand, snow samples often contain increased
460 amounts of fragments (see Table S1). For example, in protected areas in Hokkaido, the northern
461 island of Japan (Ohno & Iizuka, 2023), the majority of the MPs shapes (over 97%) were fragments,

462 with a maximum diameter < 120 µm. Snow samples from sledding hills in green areas of Krakow
463 (Lasota et al., 2023) most often contained rubber and asphalt particles from road surfaces,
464 followed by textile fibers, foil, fragments and paint particles.

465 Atmospheric transport plays an important role in the dynamics of MPs circulation in the
466 environment, especially to remote regions (Chen et al., 2023; Evangelidou et al., 2020; Y. Zhang et
467 al., 2023). Research has demonstrated that the quantity of MPs fragments diminishes
468 considerably during long-distance atmospheric transport, particularly from northern to southern
469 regions, extending into Antarctic territories. In contrast, the concentrations of MPs fibers remain
470 stable even over long trans-hemispheric distances (Chen et al., 2023). This indicates that the
471 presence of airborne MNPs is influenced by their morphology. Fibers are transported more
472 effectively – both more rapidly and over greater distances – compared to MNPs fragments, similar
473 to the behavior of non-plastic particles (Chen et al., 2023). Interestingly, due to their significant
474 elevation, meteorological conditions (wind), and unique dry and wet (snow) deposition processes,
475 glaciers can provide an insight into the long-range (or global) atmospheric transport of air
476 pollutants (Aves et al., 2022; Y. Zhang, Gao, et al., 2021).

477 Airborne MNPs can undergo mechanical and weather-related aging due to factors such as
478 collisions with mineral particles (i.e. dust and sands) (P. Liu et al., 2022) and exposure to
479 environmental conditions like UV radiation (Bianco & Passananti, 2020; Hernandez et al., 2023)
480 and temperature fluctuations, and the presence of ozone and other substances (P. Liu et al.,
481 2022). This aging processes lead to structural changes in polymers, making MPs more brittle
482 (Hernandez et al., 2023) and capable of adsorbing harmful substances like heavy metals
483 (Medyńska-Juraszek & Jadhav, 2022), which will further increase the adverse impact on living
484 organisms that inhale polluted air, and may influence the hydrosphere and soil through
485 precipitation (Y. Wang et al., 2023). Furthermore, microplastics at high altitudes may influence
486 climate change by acting as condensation nuclei in clouds, thereby affecting precipitation and
487 atmospheric processes (Y. Wang et al., 2023). Interestingly, while MPs and NPs have generally
488 been considered as inert particles, they react and interact with other pollutants (Bianco &
489 Passananti, 2020). Moreover, MPs and NPs can exhibit excessive electrostatic charge for
490 a significant period of time and can thus be carried over longer distances while attached to other
491 particles (Chen et al., 2023). For example, despite its low volatility, bisphenol A (BPA) may be
492 present in the atmosphere by adhering to solid particles (Abraham & Chakraborty, 2020).

493 Summarizing, airborne MNPs play a significant role in environmental distribution,
494 impacting terrestrial life as they settle on various surfaces plants, soil, and water surfaces and can
495 be inhaled by humans and other living organisms. Consequently, they enter the food chain and
496 can bioaccumulate at every trophic level (see Figure 5).

497 In response to ongoing industrialization and population growth, further research on the
498 presence of airborne MPs and NPs should assess possible trends and health risks, both in larger
499 urban and industrial areas and in remote or untouched areas.

500 **Figure 5. MPs circulation in the trophic pyramid**

501 **5.2. Water**

502 Plastic debris in marine environments was first reported in the 1970s (Napper &
 503 Thompson, 2020), but it did not attract much attention from the scientific community at that
 504 time. Since then, plastics pollution has increased, primarily entering water bodies through various
 505 routes, mainly through precipitation, surface runoff and wastewater (see Figure 4).

506 Precipitation is considered an important pathway for MNPs entry into water (An et al.,
 507 2024; L. Wei et al., 2023), as MPs can be suspended in the air and deposited through rainfall –
 508 contributing to reservoirs like ponds, rivers, lakes, and oceans. Storms can agitate water flows
 509 more dynamic and turbulent, resuspending sediments and circulating MPs (Hitchcock, 2020).
 510 Additionally, atmospheric processes, such as evaporation and evapotranspiration, can lift MNPs,
 511 especially fibers, back into the atmosphere from water, soil, and plants.

512 This section will focus on the current data concerning the presence of MPs in both
 513 freshwater and saltwater, while the impact on aquatic life, fauna and flora will be discussed in
 514 subsequent sections.

515 **5.2.1. Marine waters**

516 Plastic waste in sea and ocean waters began with larger items, viz. macroplastics and
 517 mega-sized plastics, like old fishing nets and packaging materials, such as plastic bags, plastic cups
 518 and straws (Napper & Thompson, 2020). Over time, research has shifted focus to smaller plastics,
 519 including MPs, which are often derived from plastic granulates used in manufacturing (Thompson

520 et al., 2004). Most plastics are buoyant, leading to their accumulation on ocean surfaces and in
521 coastal areas (Baudena et al., 2022; Huserbråten et al., 2022). Studies have documented the
522 presence of MPs like beads, fibers and fragments in various global locations (see Table S2),
523 including the Mediterranean Sea (Baudena et al., 2022), including the beaches of Alexandria
524 (Abdel Ghani et al., 2022) and Israel (Rubin et al., 2022), marine coastal regions of Singapore
525 (Curren & Yew Leong, 2023), off the coast of Florida (Kleinschmidt & Janosik, 2021), and in bays
526 off the coast of China (Y. Wei et al., 2022), Australia (Samandra et al., 2023), Germany (Stolte et
527 al., 2015), or even Iceland (Ovide et al., 2022). Research has also been conducted in waters far
528 from human life and industry, such as the Arctic (Frank et al., 2020; Lusher et al., 2015; Yakushev
529 et al., 2021) and Antarctica (Cunningham et al., 2022).

530 The source of MPs in deep sea and ocean waters cannot be clearly determined. They have
531 accumulated in the water system for decades via a complex transport and recirculation patterns
532 (Huserbråten et al., 2022). They may derive from the degradation of larger plastic components
533 transferred over long distances by sea currents, or from navigating activity such as ocean
534 transport or the naval industry and tourism (Lusher et al., 2015; Ovide et al., 2022). Alternatively,
535 MNPs may originate from runoff and wastewater from coastal areas (Marrone et al., 2021).
536 Additionally, it is assumed that the atmospheric transport from far-reaching land sources
537 contributes significantly to MPs deposition in ocean surface waters, sea ice and Arctic snow cover
538 (Y. Zhang et al., 2023).

539 While no distinct accumulation zones for MNPs are observed in open ocean waters, their
540 transport and spatiotemporal distribution is influenced by properties of the MNPs and dynamic
541 processes occurring in the ocean mixed layer, e.g. currents, waves, turbulence and convective
542 mixing (Frank et al., 2020). Notably, more MPs tend to aggregate in the subtropical gyres due to
543 local wind conditions and surface current patterns (Cózar et al., 2015; Lusher et al., 2015). MPs
544 can be retained in these ocean gyre centers for decades (Baudena et al., 2022).

545 Due to the close proximity of industrial and agricultural areas, MPs are much more diverse
546 and abundant in marine coastal waters near urbanized areas. Therefore, increased human
547 activity, including tourism, fishing and aquaculture, exerts constant pressure on the bay and coastal
548 areas and may increase pollution in coastal zones (Y. Wei et al., 2022). In addition, the abundance
549 of plastic particles in saltwater is also influenced by climatic and hydrological conditions, including
550 precipitation, as well as the characteristics of a given water body, its depth, salinity and local
551 climate (J. Liu et al., 2022; Stolte et al., 2015; Uurasjärvi et al., 2021). Additional factors include
552 reduced extent of sea ice in glaciers (Lusher et al., 2015; Yakushev et al., 2021) and long-term
553 accumulation from multiple diffuse sources and transport pathways in Antarctic waters and the
554 atmosphere (Cunningham et al., 2022).

555 ***MNPs in polar and subpolar waters***

556 The Arctic is an important temporary sink and source of MPs (Y. Zhang et al., 2023).
557 Various types of pollutant, including MPs and NPs, accumulate in sea ice, snow cover and

558 permafrost ice and may be released due to climate change (Lusher et al., 2015; Obbard et al.,
559 2014; Y. Zhang et al., 2023). Additionally, significant amounts of MPs (approximately 8-48 tons
560 per year, i.e. $1.65-9.35 \times 10^8$ MPs/s) are transported to the Arctic Ocean through the great Arctic
561 rivers (Y. Zhang et al., 2023). In the Antarctic Weddell Sea, MPs were also found in air, seawater,
562 and sediments, predominantly as fibers, indicating diverse origins from nonpoint sources and
563 various long-distance transport routes (Cunningham et al., 2022).

564 Intense fishing activities in the sub-Arctic region likely contribute to the presence of
565 plastics in Icelandic waters, both coastal nearshore waters (Ovide et al., 2022), and bottom
566 sediments around the entire island (Loughlin et al., 2021). The most common types of plastic were
567 lines (57.5%) originating from fishing gear in the water samples (Ovide et al., 2022) and fibers in
568 the sediment samples (Loughlin et al., 2021).

569 High concentrations of MPs have been reported throughout the Arctic Ocean, despite the
570 absence of significant point sources, water column suspension patterns or accumulation zones
571 (Huserbråten et al., 2022; Yakushev et al., 2021). Research conducted in Arctic waters south and
572 southwest of Svalbard, Norway, showed the presence of MPs in both surface (16 cm from the
573 top) and subsurface layers (6 m deep) (Huserbråten et al., 2022). Subsurface layers showed higher
574 concentrations, likely influenced by sampling methods and hydrological conditions. Most of the
575 detected particles (95%) were fibers. Similarly, research in Eurasian Arctic waters revealed fewer
576 MPs in surface samples compared to subsurface ones (Yakushev et al., 2021). Surface water
577 masses of Atlantic origin and discharge from the Great Siberian Rivers regulate the distribution of
578 MPs in the Eurasian Arctic.

579 ***MNPs in moderate climate waters***

580 The Baltic Sea can be mentioned as an example of brackish water, with an average salinity
581 about 7.4‰ (Meier et al., 2022). It is also quite shallow, with a mean depth of only 54 m, and
582 almost completely surrounded by land. Water stratification, caused by differences in density and
583 salinity, influences the precipitation process of MPs, which accumulate in thin layers in the
584 halocline and thermocline (Stolte et al., 2015; Uurasjärvi et al., 2021). Studies conducted in the
585 Gulf of Finland found the majority of particles to be fragments (Uurasjärvi et al., 2021). Higher
586 MPs concentrations were observed in deep-sea layers where the density of seawater changes
587 rapidly. Research conducted in the southeastern part of the Baltic Sea found higher
588 concentrations of MPs in deep layers compared to the intermediate layers (Zobkov et al., 2019).
589 The most abundant MPs types at coastal stations (depth ~30 m) were fibers. Furthermore, many
590 micropollutants have been detected in the Baltic Sea waters, including contaminants of emerging
591 concern such as personal care products (triclosan) or technical chemicals (TCPP, tris (2-
592 chloropropyl) phosphate) (Bollmann et al., 2019), which is of increasing concern as these
593 pollutants may adsorb onto the surface of MPs.

594 ***MNPs in subtropical and tropical zone waters***

595 The Mediterranean basin is a good example of marine waters in a warmer climate, with
596 hot, dry summers and cool, wet winters. In this region, anthropogenic activities have also been
597 suggested as a key factor in MPs pollution (Marrone et al., 2021). The Mediterranean basin is
598 known as a tourism center, and the coastline is also highly industrialized including inshore
599 navigation and fishing (von Schuckmann et al., 2023). The Mediterranean Sea is called the sixth
600 largest marine litter accumulation zone (Marrone et al., 2021); due to its almost closed nature, it
601 results in high plastic pollution (Baudena et al., 2022; S. Sharma et al., 2021). The distribution of
602 MPs corresponded with the results of the monitoring of the coastal waste administrated by the
603 Regional Environmental Protection Agency of Calabria (Marrone et al., 2021). The greatest levels
604 of MPs waste in seawater were noted in densely-populated areas with major commercial ports.
605 For example, high MPs densities were found in the surface waters of a beach in Alexandria, Egypt
606 (Abdel Ghani et al., 2022). Rivers also significantly contribute to microplastic pollution along the
607 Mediterranean coast, transporting pollutants from the most urbanized areas along the riverbed
608 (Rubin et al., 2022). Hence, it is clear that the amount and type of MPs in coastal areas is mainly
609 influenced by agricultural and industrial activities, but also by physical and environmental
610 conditions, such as particle size, density and water flow, and the location of collection sites
611 (Curren & Yew Leong, 2023; Marrone et al., 2021).

612 Research on the presence of MPs in equatorial climate waters in the monsoon season
613 reveals significant findings. A study of MPs in the marine coastal regions of Singapore showed
614 substantial amounts of MPs, with $9.5 \cdot 10^4$ MPs/L in the surface layer compared to $6.96 \cdot 10^4$ MPs/L
615 at greater depths, predominantly consisting of fragments (70%) (Curren & Yew Leong, 2023).
616 Additionally, higher MPs abundance was observed during the monsoon season compared to the
617 inter-monsoon season. Comparable findings for tropical coastal waters have been reported in
618 Sepanggar Bay, Sabah, Malaysia (C. N. Tang et al., 2023), in which significantly higher MPs
619 concentrations were found during the southwest monsoon. Fibers dominated in open waters, i.e.
620 Sepanggar Bay (C. N. Tang et al., 2023) and Xincun Lagoon, China (Y. Wei et al., 2022), and
621 fragments in straits, i.e. in the Johor and Singapore Straits (Curren & Yew Leong, 2023). Similar
622 conclusions regarding the increase in MPs in wet season were reported also for freshwaters, in
623 the Baotou section of the Yellow River in China (Qian et al., 2023).

624 **5.2.2. Freshwaters**

625 Freshwater ecosystems around the globe are increasingly being contaminated by MNPs,
626 a trend exacerbated by human activities and various environmental influences. MNPs have been
627 detected in water samples worldwide, predominantly in the surface waters of lakes and rivers, as
628 well as in sediments along lake shores and riverbanks (see Table S2). They have been found in the
629 Great Lakes in Canada and the USA USA (Eriksen et al., 2013), North America rivers (Castañeda et
630 al., 2014; Said & Heard, 2020), South America (Correa-Araneda et al., 2022; Drabinski et al., 2023),

631 European rivers (Mani et al., 2015; Schrank, Löder, et al., 2022; Tibbetts et al., 2018; Winkler et
632 al., 2022), Asia rivers (Kataoka et al., 2019; Y. Li et al., 2020; Lisina et al., 2021), African rivers (Saad
633 et al., 2024; Saad & Alamin, 2024), and Australia (Nan et al., 2020; Samandra et al., 2023). This
634 widespread distribution highlights the urgent need to investigate large freshwater bodies in
635 detail.

636 The Laurentian Great Lakes system has been a critical model site for studying significant
637 microplastic concentrations in surface waters. Substantial amounts of MPs have been reported
638 in the surface water layers of the Laurentian Great Lakes (Driedger et al., 2015; Eriksen et al.,
639 2013). Volunteer beach cleanups around these lakes revealed that over 80% of anthropogenic
640 litter was plastics (Driedger et al., 2015). Research on Lakes Superior, Huron, and Erie (Eriksen et
641 al., 2013) showed that Lake Erie contained the highest MPs concentration, accounting for 85% of
642 all collected particles. Despite being the smallest by volume and shallowest of the Great Lakes,
643 Lake Erie's dense population (Lake Erie Lakewide Action, 2011) heightens its exposure to
644 anthropogenic activities, including agriculture, industry, and urbanization. Pellets and fragments
645 were the most abundant MPs overall (Driedger et al., 2015; Eriksen et al., 2013). The dominance
646 of pellets and fragments in these waters points to additional MPs sources, such as consumer
647 goods and personal care products.

648 Personal care products, notably those containing microbeads, are among the recognized
649 contributors to MPs pollution in freshwater systems. Multi-colored spherical particles from items
650 like facial cleansers have been found floating in freshwater (Eriksen et al., 2013). The use of
651 microbeads in cosmetics is now banned in many countries, including the USA and Canada (see
652 section 6). Interestingly, in Lake Winnipeg – Canada's fifth-largest lake – no micro-pellets or beads
653 were detected in three years of sampling (Anderson et al., 2017); instead, fibers were dominant,
654 while films and foam were rare. Lake Winnipeg exhibited higher MPs densities than Lakes Huron
655 and Superior and comparable levels to Lake Erie (Anderson et al., 2017; Eriksen et al., 2013).
656 Although microbead bans mitigate certain forms of MPs pollution, other particle types persist,
657 prompting a closer look at how lakes elsewhere in the world exhibit unique MPs profiles.

658 Lakes in different regions reveal diverse MPs compositions, reflecting local activities and
659 waste management practices. In Laguna de Bay, the largest freshwater lake in the Philippines, the
660 mean MPs density is 14.29 MPs/m³, with fibers making up 57%, fragments 21%, and foil 17%,
661 while granules and filaments appear in smaller quantities. PP, EVA, and PET together account for
662 65% of all MPs (Arcadio et al., 2022). This contamination has been linked to personal protective
663 equipment (e.g., disposable face masks) and the use of plastic bags and other plastics in fishing.
664 Such findings underscore how everyday plastic usage contributes to MPs contamination, which
665 can also alter the chemical properties of plastics.

666 Chemical transformations of microplastics, including metal sorption, add complexity to
667 MPs pollution in freshwater systems. In Red Hills Lake in India, various metals were detected on
668 MPs surfaces, notably aluminum, iron, silicon, and calcium (Gopinath et al., 2020). The likely

669 sources of these metals include fishing activities and surrounding industrial plants. As industrial
670 and municipal sources continue to introduce MPs into water bodies, wastewater treatment plants
671 (WWTPs) emerge as a key point source to examine (Y. Li et al., 2023). By understanding WWTP-
672 related MPs emissions, we set the stage for examining how rivers – key conduits connecting land
673 to ocean – further transport these particles.

674 Rivers are crucial for supplying drinking water and for the transfer of MNPs from inland
675 areas to marine ecosystem. Studies have explored MPs in both surface water and river sediments,
676 revealing how local factors such as population density, WWTP systems, hydrological conditions,
677 and reservoirs affect MPs loads (Lisina et al., 2021). It is estimated that rivers transfer around 70–
678 80% of MPs to coastal and oceanic systems (Drabinski et al., 2023, p. 20). For example, the
679 Yangtze River in China is a major source of plastics entering the ocean (Gao et al., 2023; Y. Li et
680 al., 2020), with the Three Gorges Dam retaining about 22 (± 20.5) tons of MPs per day, which
681 accounts for nearly half of what would otherwise flow into the ocean daily. PE is the most
682 prevalent polymer, comprising 54.5–82.0% of MPs; other polymers include PP, PET, PVC, PA, PS,
683 PUR, and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). Most detected particles (75.7%) measure 10–300 μm . In
684 Southeast Asia, seasonal changes also affect MPs composition and abundance (Qian et al., 2023).
685 These findings highlight how river systems, such as the Volga, exhibit spatial variations in MPs
686 profiles, providing a prime example of how downstream populations and industries exacerbate
687 pollution.

688 The Volga River illustrates how industrial activity and population centers influence
689 microplastic concentrations. In the Volga River, MPs appear in all surface water samples,
690 predominantly as fragments (41%), fibers (37%), and films (22%), with an average of 0.90 MPs/ m^3
691 (0.21 mg/ m^3) (Lisina et al., 2021). Concentrations peak downstream of WWTPs in larger cities,
692 whereas upstream levels are notably lower. These patterns parallel findings in other rivers, where
693 differing land uses, and plastic degradation pathways generate a variety of MPs shapes and sizes.

694 Plastics used in packaging and consumer products often degrade into fragments,
695 microspheres, and films that vary across river systems. Fragments (microspheres or microbeads)
696 and films typically derive from packaging and manufacturing processes (Castañeda et al., 2014;
697 Kumayon et al., 2023). In the South Saskatchewan River, MPs concentrations vary by sampling
698 site, likely due to surface runoff and land use (Kumayon et al., 2023). Conversely, in the Jamuna
699 River in Bangladesh, fibers dominate (70%), with foil, line, fragments, and foam at 14%, 10%, 4%,
700 and 2%, respectively (Khan & Setu, 2022). Colored plastics prevail overall, posing risks to aquatic
701 organisms that may mistake them for food (Gopinath et al., 2020; Jabeen et al., 2017). Such
702 regional differences underscore the complexity of MPs pollution, setting the stage to examine
703 Australian urban rivers flowing into Port Phillip Bay.

704 Urban rivers in Australia reflect global MPs trends, with high concentrations and varied
705 particle sizes posing ecological concerns. Four urban rivers flowing into Port Phillip Bay near
706 Melbourne contain, on average, 37 ± 9 MPs/L, with a mean particle size of 76 ± 48 μm , mostly

707 below 99 μm (Samandra et al., 2023). PA and PP were the most abundant (27% and 24%,
708 respectively), followed by PET and PC at 16%, then PE, PS, and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA)
709 each at 5%. Secondary MPs dominate, as almost all were fragments resembling microspheres or
710 pellets (Samandra et al., 2023). These findings align with patterns seen in heavily industrialized
711 rivers elsewhere – particularly in Europe’s Rhine Basin.

712 The Rhine River exemplifies how population density and industrialization magnify
713 microplastic loads, echoing patterns found worldwide. A study of the Rhine River over an 820-km
714 stretch between Basel and Rotterdam (Mani et al., 2015) demonstrated rising MPs levels
715 downstream, corresponding to denser populations and more industrial facilities. Concentrations
716 reached a mean of 17.061 MPs/ m^3 , with fragments being the most common (37.5%), followed by
717 opaque beads (45.2%), transparent beads (13.2%), fibers (2.5%), and others (1.1%). Another
718 investigation (Schrank, Löder, et al., 2022) on the Rhine and Danube also showed a dominance of
719 fragments ($90.7 \pm 13.6\%$), with over half ($<300 \mu\text{m}$) and the main polymers being PE (49.2%) and
720 PP (33.2%). Surface water plastic concentrations ranged from 0.7 to 354.9 MPs/ m^3 .

721 These instances highlight the threats posed by plastic pollution to both freshwater and
722 marine ecosystems, prompting to consider the larger challenge of effectively mitigating and
723 managing MNPs across various scales.

724 **5.2.3. Drinking water**

725 A mentioned, freshwater rivers play a key role in providing sources of drinking water, but
726 environmental pollutants present in these waters may enter drinking water through water
727 treatment processes. Disordered water and wastewater management increase the risk of
728 environmental pollution and the inflow of various types of POPs, which will be harmful to aquatic
729 life. Additionally, pollutants such as heavy metals can interact with MPs (Medyńska-Juraszek &
730 Jadhav, 2022). Adsorbed pollutants as well as plastic additives may later be released into the tap
731 water due to aging and degradation processes of MPs (see Figure 2).

732 Therefore, public authorities should strive to close water cycles, organize water and
733 wastewater management by creating sewage networks and wastewater treatment, but also
734 manage rainwater outflows. However, to the best of our knowledge, there are currently no
735 specific legal regulations limiting the occurrence of MPs in WWTPs effluent or in tap water.

736 ***MNPs in groundwater***

737 Insufficient water source protection, as well as disordered water management may lead
738 to the contamination of groundwater intended for drinking. Karst groundwater is one of the most
739 important sources of drinking water in rural areas, such as Guizhou Province in China, where
740 water sources are often dispersed (An et al., 2022; J. Tang et al., 2023). In water samples from
741 karst caves in Xixiu District, the MPs count was on average 4.5 MPs/L (2.33-9.50 MPs/L). The main
742 types of MPs were foil and fiber, both colored and transparent, and most often consisted of PS
743 and PE, with a size of 1–5 mm (An et al., 2022). Hence, in addition to landfill leachates,

744 groundwater is at risk of contamination from airborne pollution that has settled on the ground
745 and leaked through the soil into the aquifer. MPs can also be washed deep through the soil
746 surface by the activity of organisms such as earthworms (*Lumbricus terrestris*) (Yu et al., 2019).
747 A study examining water from five wells located close (100-1000 m) to the landfill in Da Nang city,
748 Vietnam (Thao et al., 2022), found concentrations of 2 to 21 MPs/L, with the dominant shapes
749 being fragments and fibers (87.67 and 12.33%, respectively), and the most prevalent material
750 being PET (68.5%). These numbers are quite high compared to other reported levels in well water
751 or surface water (see Table S2).

752 **Water treatment processes**

753 Classical water treatment systems based on coagulation and filtration processes
754 effectively remove solid particles (Barbier et al., 2022; Dalmau-Soler et al., 2021). Therefore, it is
755 expected that most of the solid pollutants, including MPs present in the intake water, will be
756 retained in the system. However, recent studies prove that MPs are present in the outflow from
757 WTP, i.e. in drinking water (Barbier et al., 2022; Dalmau-Soler et al., 2021; Sharifi & Movahedian
758 Attar, 2022). In a drinking water treatment plant (DWTP) in Iran, the MPs removal efficiencies
759 were found to be 57.7% in the filtration stage and 26% in the clarification stage, while the total
760 efficiency was 83.7%. The abundance of MPs at the DWTP outflow was 260.5 ± 48.9 MPs/L (Sharifi
761 & Movahedian Attar, 2022). DWTP in Barcelona effectively removes microplastics present along
762 the Llobregat basin (Dalmau-Soler et al., 2021). The MPs removal efficiency in coagulation and
763 sand filtration processes was $78 \pm 9\%$, with the total efficiency of the plant at $93 \pm 5\%$. The mean
764 MPs concentration at the outlet was 0.06 ± 0.04 MPs/L. Barbier et al. conducted research for
765 three French DWTPs, one of which additionally used microfiltration and nanofiltration membrane
766 processes (Barbier et al., 2022). The number of MPs at the outlet of the DWTP was up to 0.260
767 MPs/L, with an overall removal rate above 99%. In all mentioned studies, the most common MPs
768 were PE and PP, with PET in the Iranian DWTP, PTFE (polytetrafluoroethylene) in the French
769 DWTPs, and polyester (PES) instead of PE in the Spanish DWTP.

770 **MNPs in bottled water and food products**

771 Despite strict quality requirements for the production of bottled water, research has
772 revealed that the chemical, physical and microbiological properties of certain bottled water
773 brands do not meet national and international standards, particularly in developing countries
774 (Ghanbarian et al., 2022). This also applies to the presence of MPs and NPs in bottled mineral
775 water (Ghanbarian et al., 2022; E.-H. Lee et al., 2021; H. Li et al., 2023; Mason et al., 2018; Oßmann
776 et al., 2018). Small-size MPs ($<5\mu\text{m}$) have been detected in water stored in both disposable and
777 reusable PET bottles, as well as in glass bottles (Oßmann et al., 2018). In disposable bottles, the
778 dominant MPs was PET in variable amounts of $2,649 \pm 2,857$ MPs/L. In contrast, glass bottles
779 exhibited a significantly higher contamination level of $6,292 \pm 10,521$ MPs/L in glass bottles, with
780 different polymers dominating, such as PE or styrene-butadiene copolymer (Oßmann et al., 2018).
781 For reusable bottles, contamination sources may include the bottle cap, the washing process or

782 other stages of production or refilling. In a similar study by Mason et al., most of bottled water
783 tested contained MPs, primarily composed of fragments (66%) and fibers, with a mean
784 concentration of 10.4 MPs/L (Mason et al., 2018). Additionally, research by Li et al. found a higher
785 mean amount of MPs in bottled water (72.32 ± 44.64 MPs/L) than in tap water (49.67 ± 17.49
786 MPs/L) (H. Li et al., 2023). The most common forms were foils, consisting mainly of cellulose and
787 PVC.

788 MNPs have also been detected in other liquid food products, including bottled beverages
789 like white wine (Prata, Paço, et al., 2020), honey, beer, milk and skimmed milk and energy drinks
790 (Vitali et al., 2023). However, it is important to note that the reliability of these findings may be
791 in question due to the lack of available validated methods and specific guidelines for analysis and
792 sampling, or concentration limits in food or drinking water.

793 As mentioned, contamination of bottled water with MPs and NPs primarily originates from
794 the packaging material used in the bottles and caps. In many instances, plastic monomers may
795 leak from the bottle walls into the water under high or cold conditions during manufacturing,
796 transport and storage (Ghanbarian et al., 2022). Pursuing the development of alternative water
797 treatment systems, such treatments specially for bottled water or domestic water use, may be
798 useful, although it does not seem advisable. Future research on the presence of MNPs in drinking
799 water, including both tap and bottled varieties, should focus on analyzing the smallest particles
800 that may pose adverse health risks.

801 **5.3. Sediments**

802 Even with the most advanced treatment methods, massive amounts of MNPs, mainly
803 fibers, can still be released into the environment along with the treated wastewater stream. And
804 these MNPs can subsequently accumulate in the sediments of rivers and lakes. In addition, river
805 and marine processes and topographic features (e.g. terrain and ground forms, vegetation,
806 sediment layer thickness) also play important roles in the transfer of microplastics from river
807 basins to ocean waters (Ockelford et al., 2020; B. Yuan et al., 2023).

808 Human activities therefore directly contribute to the accumulation of MNPs in river and
809 lake sediments. Heavier MNPs particles sink to the bottom due to gravity, while lighter, low-
810 density, and low-mass particles, such as fibers or films, may form larger clusters or agglomerates.
811 These lighter particles can also settle on other pollutants or adhere to the surfaces of aquatic
812 plants (F. Xia et al., 2021). Consequently, the transportation of MNPs to sediments occurs through
813 both sinking and floating processes, which are influenced by the mechanical interactions between
814 colloidal particles suspended in the water column, e.g. clays, and MPs particles (Mendrik et al.,
815 2023). Furthermore, MPs settled on the bottom of a basin may infiltrate deeper sediment layers
816 (B. Yuan et al., 2023). Additionally, small-sized MPs (50–500 μm) are particularly prone to re-
817 suspension due to disturbances at the water-sediment interface, e.g. due to boat traffic or fishing
818 in a reservoir (F. Xia et al., 2021).

819 Although MPs are broadly similar to natural sediments in terms of size, shape, or density,
820 their properties change over time due to degradation, fragmentation, or deformation. As such, it
821 is much more difficult to understand their behavior and predict their influence on the
822 environment (Waldschläger et al., 2022). However, the concentration of microplastics in
823 a sediment is often positively related to the clay fraction, indicating that MPs demonstrate similar
824 dynamics to clay sediment particles in the transport process (X. Sun et al., 2021). Additionally,
825 rainfall and seasonality can also affect the abundance of microplastics in sediment samples, with
826 higher abundance observed during the rainy season compared to the dry season (Ockelford et al.,
827 2020; Y. Wei et al., 2022).

828 The presence of MPs in sediments can also vary significantly depending on the location
829 and land use of a given water body (Dhivert et al., 2024; Townsend et al., 2019). For example,
830 MPs in sediment samples have been observed in wetlands (Townsend et al., 2019; Wen et al.,
831 2022), and are often found in higher amounts in stations/points in outer bays compared to those
832 in inner bays (Y. Wei et al., 2022). The rainy season favors the accumulation of smaller MPs in
833 river sediments along the direction of river flow; however, the amount of MPs in sediments was
834 slightly higher in the dry season than in the rainy season (F. Xia et al., 2021). Moreover, the
835 amount of MPs in river estuaries is much higher than along its length or on the sea coast
836 (Rodrigues et al., 2022). However, due to the variation in local pollution sources and
837 hydrodynamic conditions between regions, any comparison between studies is difficult
838 (Rodrigues et al., 2022).

839 The occurrence of a given polymer type in river sediment samples has been associated
840 with the type of local contamination from specific industrial sources (Dhivert et al., 2024). In
841 addition, grain size, total organic content, and high organic matter content can also influence the
842 presence and abundance of MPs in sediments, although the relationship between these factors
843 and MPs abundance may not always be statistically significant (Loughlin et al., 2021).

844 Factors such as runoff from nearby areas, entrapment of plastic debris by vegetation, and
845 the sinking or floating of particles of different sizes can influence the abundance of microplastics
846 in lake sediments (Dilshad et al., 2022). In addition, significant roles are also played by
847 hydrosedimentation processes (Dhivert et al., 2024).

848 Microplastic sedimentation is a long-term process that depends on water flow rates,
849 atmospheric conditions, and the size and shape of microplastic particles. It can result in MPs being
850 present higher levels in sediments than in surface waters (Loughlin et al., 2021).

851 Similarly, the accumulation of microplastics in marine sediments is influenced by *inter alia*
852 fishing, aquaculture and wastewater from washing cycles (Y. Wei et al., 2022). Microplastics may
853 be more abundant in these sediments due to their high organic matter content in sediments and
854 low-energy intermolecular interactions. Various types of polymers have been identified in marine
855 sediments, including rayon, PE, PS, PP, PET, PA or acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) (Coppock
856 et al., 2017).

857 MPs can accumulate in sediments as a result of ingestion and excretion by aquatic
858 organisms, transfer to larger predators, sinking with dead organisms, or defecation. Sediment can
859 also increase the bioaccumulation of microplastics and other contaminants, leading to their
860 biomagnification (Brittain, 2018; Nava & Leoni, 2021). This can lead to changes in the interactions
861 and adsorption between MPs and sediment particles.

862 Nonetheless, there is a need for further research to understand the mechanics of MNPs
863 deposition and transport in sediments (B. He et al., 2020). Future studies should focus on
864 identifying the sources, transport mechanisms, and potential ecological effects of MNPs in the
865 sediments of rivers, lakes, and saline waters.

866 **5.4. Wastewater**

867 Studies show that wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) effluent is the main route of
868 MNPs transfer to aquatic ecosystems and soil (Yaseen et al., 2022). At the same time, it is
869 important to note that WWTPs significantly reduce the flow of MNPs at various treatment
870 processes. Considering both of the above, this subsection will provide a more in-depth
871 exploration in this topic, which will allow to show on the one hand the sources and amounts of
872 MNPs in wastewater, and on the other hand the possibilities of their retention in subsequent
873 treatment stages, and thus the highlighting the efficiency of modern WWTPs and future
874 perspectives.

875 ***Characteristics and occurrence of MNPs in wastewater***

876 In urban wastewater, the dominant type of MNPs are fibers (Acarer, 2023; Bayo et al.,
877 2021; Ben-David et al., 2021). This phenomenon can be attributed to the release of large amounts
878 of fibers from households, i.e. through laundry and washing activities (Acarer, 2023; Bayo et al.,
879 2021; Ben-David et al., 2021). It is estimated that, on average, each person emits approximately
880 1145 MPs particles daily through domestic sewage (Vercauteren et al., 2023).

881 In addition, in urban agglomerations, large amounts of particles and car tire fragments
882 also enter WWTPs through the combined sewer system. This pollution is also compounded by
883 urban runoff, especially storm water, which carries road pollution such as particles from tire wear
884 (Obermaier & Pistocchi, 2022; Vercauteren et al., 2023), and by industrial wastewater inflows
885 after initial treatment (Morris et al., 2022; Rodríguez-Vidal et al., 2022; Umar et al., 2023).

886 Microfibers in wastewater mainly come from textiles and clothing made of synthetic
887 materials (Acarer, 2023; Bayo et al., 2021). The polymers most commonly used in clothing
888 manufacturing are PES and PA (Rackov et al., 2023), with PES fibers accounting for the largest
889 proportion of wastewater entering urban WWTPs (Lares et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2019; Ziajahromi
890 et al., 2017; Zou et al., 2021). However, fibers made from other types of polymers are also present
891 in large quantities, e.g. PE (Alavian Petroody et al., 2020; Cao et al., 2020; Pittura et al., 2021; Ren
892 et al., 2020), PP (Ren et al., 2020; Y. Zhang, Wang, et al., 2021), and PA (X. Liu et al., 2019;
893 Ziajahromi et al., 2017). Research indicates that washing synthetic textiles at 40°C results in the

894 release of a considerable number of microfibers (Rackov et al., 2023). To minimize this microfiber
895 release, consumers may change their habits, e.g. wash at low temperatures, avoid long wash
896 cycles with fully loaded washing machines, or use fabric softeners and washing machine filters
897 (Bayo et al., 2021). Individual consumer choices can therefore reduce the contribution of
898 microplastics entering WWTPs and subsequently impacting the environment (Conley et al., 2019).

899 Studies have also confirmed the presence of other shapes of MPs in municipal wastewater,
900 including irregularly-shaped fragments, although these occur in smaller quantities (Bayo et al.,
901 2020; X. Liu et al., 2019; Mason et al., 2016). Their presence may suggest partial degradation of
902 the MNPs. Other MPs found in wastewater include microspheres (Hidayaturrahman & Lee, 2019),
903 which may come from personal care products and cosmetics, as well as foams, foils and pellets
904 (Mason et al., 2016). The high presence of LDPE film in wastewater may be attributed to the close
905 proximity of WWTP to agricultural greenhouses, along with the continued demand for disposable
906 bags and plastic packaging (Bayo et al., 2020). Additionally, wastewater from plastic recycling
907 facilities predominantly contains PE fragments (Umar et al., 2023).

908 MPs of a wide range of sizes have been identified at the inlets of municipal WWTPs. For
909 example, in a WWTP in west Iran, plastic particles ranging from 1 to 4750 μm were noted, with
910 65.8% measuring 1-25 μm (Asadi et al., 2023). Other studies reported average sizes of polymer
911 particles in wastewater in the range of 20-300 μm (J.-H. Lee et al., 2023), 100-500 μm (Xu et al.,
912 2019), or 8-550 μm (Ren et al., 2020). Microplastic fibers and fragments were abundant in various
913 colors, e.g. red, black (Ren et al., 2020) and transparent (X. Liu et al., 2019) or black-colored MPs
914 like tire wear particles (Obermaier & Pistocchi, 2022).

915 The occurrence of MPs in wastewater may demonstrated both spatial and temporal
916 variations. Some studies have found the types of MPs to vary with the season (Dalu et al., 2021),
917 while others have not (Bayo et al., 2020). While the former found no clear patterns in relation to
918 wastewater treatment technology, the number of MPs differed between wet season and high air
919 temperature conditions (Dalu et al., 2021). It has been proposed that untreated wastewater may
920 periodically be discharged into the Baltic Sea in response to climate change and urbanization;
921 such discharges are associated with sanitary sewer overflow caused by the low technological or
922 hydraulic capacity of WWTPs located in the Baltic catchment area (Baresel & Olshammar, 2018).
923 Similarly, for wetlands, which are used for wastewater post-treatment, an increase in the amount
924 of MPs was observed during the rainy season, possibly due to atmospheric precipitation
925 (Büngener et al., 2023). MPs contamination also varies depending on geographical distribution
926 (Sadia et al., 2022), with higher MPs particle numbers being observed in wastewater in tourist
927 areas (Franco et al., 2023); however, high concentrations of MPs also occurred in rural treatment
928 plants where advanced wastewater treatment technologies are lacking (S. Wei et al., 2020).

929 ***Classical treatment processes***

930 WWTPs play an important role in removing high levels of microplastic particles, achieving
931 removal efficiencies that can range from one to three orders of magnitude (Obermaier &

932 Pistocchi, 2022). Nevertheless, substantial amounts of MPs continue to be discharged along with
933 treated wastewater (Flores-Munguía et al., 2023; Sadia et al., 2022), leading to bioaccumulation
934 in the environment (Kwon et al., 2022) (see Table S3). Considering daily wastewater flows, these
935 amounts can range from several million to several billion MPs per day (Magni et al., 2019;
936 Vercauteren et al., 2023; F. Yuan et al., 2021; Y. Zhang, Wang, et al., 2021). The choice of
937 wastewater treatment technology and its possible post-treatment or advanced methods is
938 therefore of great importance (F. Yuan et al., 2021).

939 In addition to the type of treatment process, the efficiency of MPs removal is influenced
940 by the physicochemical properties of the polymer, such as its density, particle size, charge, and
941 hydrophobicity (Umar et al., 2023). As noted, fibers represent the most prevalent subtype of
942 MNPs entering WWTPs. These fibers present more serious problem compared to particles, which
943 are typically retained more effectively during treatment (Acarer, 2023; Ben-David et al., 2021;
944 Lares et al., 2018). Nonetheless, studies indicate that fibers are removed effectively (Asadi et al.,
945 2023). Therefore, it is crucial for wastewater treatment system designers, practitioners, and
946 policymakers to understand the morphology and origins of MNPs (Abeynayaka et al., 2022).

947 Different wastewater treatment technologies demonstrate different MPs removal
948 efficiencies; as such, they release MPs into the environment as point sources to varying degrees
949 (Acarer, 2023; Carr et al., 2016; Sturm et al., 2023), or can increase coastal zone pollution (Akarsu
950 et al., 2020).

951 Most municipal WWTPs are designed according to a common scheme (Mason et al., 2016;
952 S. Singh et al., 2021), i.e. a basic treatment allowing mechanical removal of large particles with
953 a diameter of 1.5-6 mm or greater (Raju et al., 2020; Sharifi et al., 2023; S. Singh et al., 2021).
954 Most MPs are removed at the primary treatment stage (Hernández Fernández et al., 2022), during
955 which these particles are retained on coarse screens and fine screens (Sharifi et al., 2023). More
956 than 70% of plastic fibers in all sizes can be removed in the primary settling tank itself (Alavian
957 Petroody et al., 2020). Primary treatment has been found to achieve roughly 75% MPs removal
958 efficiency (Hidayaturrehman & Lee, 2019; Kwon et al., 2022). MPs particles with a diameter
959 greater than 500 μm are removed in the primary settling tank, and particles $<500 \mu\text{m}$ are
960 removed in the clarifier unit (Alavian Petroody et al., 2020). However, polymer fibers often enter
961 further treatment stages (Kurt et al., 2022).

962 In a typical WWTP, suspended and dissolved organic material and nutrients are removed
963 during a secondary treatment stage, most often through aerated activated sludge chambers and
964 sedimentation in secondary settling tanks (Raju et al., 2020; Sharifi et al., 2023). During this
965 treatment stage, a crucial role in MPs removal is played by gravitational settling and adsorption
966 on flocs (B. Zhang et al., 2023). An important role is played by activated sludge as MNPs can be
967 adsorbed and desorbed on flocs (Hao & Shen, 2021). It is reported that biological treatment and
968 sedimentation can reduce MPs levels by 90 to 96.6% (Hernández Fernández et al., 2022;
969 Hidayaturrehman & Lee, 2019). Additionally, it should be emphasized that the degree of sludge

970 recirculation in the activated sludge chamber supports MPs removal due to further adsorption on
971 the stabilized flocs (B. Zhang et al., 2023). For example, a Korean WWTP employed a filter plate
972 covered with activated carbon to increase the adaptability and adhesion of microorganisms,
973 resulting in the removal of 91.04% of microplastics (Kwon et al., 2022); however, the
974 concentration of MPs in effluent was still rather high (190 MPs/L), and higher than the MPs level
975 detected in the nearby river. It needs to be noted that the quantity and quality of MPs identified
976 in wastewater are influenced by both the sampling technique and identification method, and as
977 such, any comparisons between studies must be approached with caution.

978 ***Post-treatment***

979 Although pretreatment processes and the activated sludge system can effectively remove
980 MNPs (Koyuncuoğlu & Erden, 2023), wastewater is subjected to additional processes before being
981 released into the environment. The simplest solution seems to be the coagulation-flocculation-
982 sedimentation system, which is commonly used in surface water purification systems with a high
983 organic matter load and high turbidity (Girish et al., 2023). The type of coagulant has been found
984 to influence removal efficiency. Organic coagulants, such as polyamines, are less effective at
985 removing MPs with a diameter of less than 10 µm than inorganic coagulants such as iron chloride
986 or polyaluminum chloride. Laboratory tests conducted on treated municipal wastewater treated
987 with PS microspheres (diameter up to 10 µm) indicated up to 99.4% removal by coagulation
988 (Rajala et al., 2020). However, similar removal efficiency might be achieved for actual urban
989 wastewater by using coagulation in the primary treatment before the primary settling tank, as
990 confirmed by Jachimowicz and Cydzik-Kwiatkowska (Jachimowicz & Cydzik-Kwiatkowska, 2022).
991 In addition, the use of chemical coagulants may negatively affect the biological wastewater
992 treatment processes. Natural coagulants, such as chitosan or starch, allow MPs removal efficiency
993 levels of 90-95% (Girish et al., 2023), making them an attractive alternative to chemicals. Low-
994 cost coagulants, such as those made from plants or food waste, although effective in improving
995 the clarity of wastewater, have limited value in removing microplastics (Reza et al., 2023).

996 ***Advanced and alternative technologies***

997 Depending on the needs of specific tertiary treatment, alternative processes such as
998 coagulation/flocculation, adsorption, or advanced oxidation, but largely rely on surface or depth
999 filtration can be used (Bitter et al., 2022). Advanced wastewater treatment systems are highly
1000 effective and provide >99% removal of MPs (Parashar & Hait, 2023). Combining multiple
1001 purification processes can significantly minimize MPs outflow into the environment (Günes-
1002 Durak, 2021). However, it should be remembered that the main goal of most advanced
1003 purification systems is to remove dissolved contaminants, and not dispersed solid particles such
1004 as MPs; hence, despite their very high effectiveness, advanced methods do not allow for the
1005 complete removal of microplastics (Sturm et al., 2023). For example, the use of additional
1006 membrane disc filters (Salmi et al., 2021; Simon et al., 2019) ensured the removal of 99% of
1007 microplastics from wastewater (outflow 0.8 MPs/L; disc-filter pore size 10 µm) (Salmi et al.,

1008 2021). Moreover, the use of a coagulation process with an aluminum coagulant followed by a disk
1009 filter allowed better microplastic removal than the disk filter used alone (Kwon et al., 2022).
1010 Likewise, adding ozonation as an advanced oxidation process also provides very high efficiency
1011 (>99%) in MPs removal (Hidayaturrahman & Lee, 2019; Parashar & Hait, 2023). Furthermore, the
1012 combination of an up-flow granular anaerobic sludge blanket and an anaerobic membrane
1013 bioreactor removed 94% of MPs (87% of fibers and 100% of fragments); by comparison, the classic
1014 activated sludge system removed an average of 86% (Pittura et al., 2021).

1015 Current advanced technologies are not cost-effective for capturing very fine MPs and
1016 fiber-shaped particles (Freeman et al., 2020). However, nature-based solutions (NBS), such as
1017 aerated ponds (Arregocés-Garcés et al., 2024) or wetland systems are effective and relatively
1018 inexpensive (Büngener et al., 2023; S. Wei et al., 2020). The wetland design is very important.
1019 While an integrated full-scale free-water surface constructed wetland (CW) incorporated into
1020 a municipal wastewater treatment scheme yielded high MPs retention efficiency (95% MPs,
1021 runoff 0.30 ± 0.09 MPs/L) (Bydalek et al., 2023), the runoff quality in surface flow wetlands was
1022 strongly influenced by atmospheric MPs, with the MPs load increasing significantly after flowing
1023 through a reed-based surface flow wetland (Büngener et al., 2023). Horizontal/vertical CW
1024 subsurface flow offers an MPs removal rate greater than 88%, compared to 37.5% in CW surface
1025 flow (Y. Li et al., 2023). MPs number is also influenced by the type and density of vegetation cover
1026 (Y. Li et al., 2023), and the removal of MPs in CWs is strongly influenced by the porosity of the
1027 backfill gravel and hydraulic retention time (Y. Li et al., 2023; S. Wei et al., 2020).

1028 Despite their high efficiency, MNPs outflows from tertiary WWTPs or from NBS remain
1029 significant and could have a considerable impact on the environment, particularly concerning the
1030 smallest NPs. Although the high MNPs removal rates offered by advanced tertiary systems offer
1031 promise for their reuse in agricultural irrigation (Pittura et al., 2021), high numbers of smaller MPs
1032 fractions, like fibers, may be released into the soil; as such, the use of sewage for irrigation can
1033 increase the spread of MNPs in the terrestrial environment. Further research is needed to assess
1034 how far these MNPs infiltrate in the soil profile and whether they may therefore contaminate
1035 shallow aquifers (Uddin et al., 2022).

1036 ***Industrial wastewater***

1037 Industrial wastewater can be treated by a range of processes including oxidation, physical,
1038 biological and physicochemical methods (Barkmann-Metaj et al., 2023; Halepoto et al., 2022).
1039 Often, the nature of production determines the processes used. For example, in industrial
1040 wastewater from the Song Than 1 Industrial Park, derived from *inter alia* plastics and packaging
1041 factories, and textile and dyeing factories, the predominant MPs types were fragments in the
1042 form of granulates (56.46%) and flakes and fibers (each about 20%) (Hai et al., 2020). The
1043 proposed flocculation method using Fe-based coagulation process ensures stable removal
1044 efficiency and is more resistant to water pollution load changes and is a rather simple and
1045 inexpensive method. The removal efficiency was found to be 98% for microplastic granules, 87%

1046 for fragments and 83% for fibers (Hai et al., 2020). Closed cycles with raw material recovery are
1047 often used in industry. Purification and wastewater reuse in the plastics industry is profitable, it
1048 also allows more efficient use of existing water resources, minimizes the discharge of hazardous
1049 pollutants into the environment (Halepoto et al., 2022), and will also allow for the recovery of
1050 raw materials. Such solutions are consistent with the assumptions of the circular economy
1051 adopted by the United Nations (UNEP, 2022b).

1052 ***Environmental fate***

1053 MNPs as mentioned earlier, can transport chemicals with toxic or endocrine effects into
1054 the aquatic environment. For example, estrogens present in wastewater can be adsorbed on LDPE
1055 and PET microplastics (Al-Jandal et al., 2022). MNPs should be considered as new carriers of
1056 pollution including heavy metals or polychlorinated biphenyls (Bayo et al., 2016). Particles and
1057 fibers may be accessible to various organisms and, for example, be mistaken for food by fish living
1058 near the outlet of treated wastewater into the river (Al-Jandal et al., 2022). Micro- and
1059 nanoplastics can also affect the stability of the purification process itself, including operational
1060 and process stability (Enfrin et al., 2019). Moreover, MPs can destabilize the anaerobic digestion
1061 process by limiting the activity of microorganisms involved in fermentation or by inducing an
1062 increase in the number of antibiotic resistance genes (Kong et al., 2023).

1063 ***Current legal situation of MNPs in wastewater***

1064 While WWTPs are not usually designed to eliminate MNPs, a significant portion of plastic
1065 particles can be removed throughout the treatment process. To reduce the release of MPs from
1066 urban sources, proper management of urban and road runoff as well as overflows in collective
1067 sewer systems should be ensured (Obermaier & Pistocchi, 2022).

1068 In December 2024, the European Union issued a directive requiring Member States to
1069 monitor MPs in wastewater and sludge for WWTPs with a population equivalent of more than
1070 10,000 (European Parliament, 2024). Nevertheless, there are no regulations limiting MNPs in
1071 wastewater discharged to the environment. Before guidelines are established, further research
1072 is needed on various wastewater treatment systems affecting the fate of MPs (Büngener et al.,
1073 2023), as well as providing detailed, uniform guidelines for sample collection, processing and
1074 analysis.

1075 **5.5. Sludge**

1076 The majority of MPs (up to 99%) that enter WWTPs are deposited in the sludge at
1077 subsequent treatment stages (Y. Hu et al., 2019; Obermaier & Pistocchi, 2022; Uddin et al., 2022).
1078 Sewage sludge, i.e. the primary by-product of the treatment process, will therefore be enriched
1079 with various types and categories of MPs present in the wastewater.

1080 The size distribution and composition of MPs in sewage sludge may vary depending on
1081 geographical location, timing and frequency of sampling, sludge treatment method, or the

1082 presence of different types of plastics. The main types of MPs found in sludge are fibers and
1083 fragments (di Bella et al., 2022; Gies et al., 2018; Y. Hu et al., 2019). For example, in conventional
1084 activated sludge installations, most MPs in the sludge were fragments, while fibers were the most
1085 common type from a WWTPs with a membrane bioreactor (di Bella et al., 2022). Films, beads and
1086 other particles also occur in sludge (di Bella et al., 2022; Gies et al., 2018; Y. Hu et al., 2019).
1087 Studies have found the most common polymers to be low-density ones such as PE and PP (Gao
1088 et al., 2023; Menéndez-Manjón et al., 2022) and acrylic fibers, PA, alkyd resin and PS (Y. Hu et al.,
1089 2019; V. K. Singh, 2022). The occurrence of low-density MPs can be explained by their entrapment
1090 in flocs, caused by their random polarity and higher sorption potential (Edo et al., 2020). However,
1091 the sludge is also abundant in higher density polymers like polyethyl acrylate PMA (Gies et al.,
1092 2018), PET and ABS or rubber as wear tire particles (Gao et al., 2023; Obermaier & Pistocchi,
1093 2022). Moreover, the presence of glitter particles (Raju et al., 2018) (often made of PET or PVC)
1094 has been demonstrated, which is related to the consumption of personal hygiene products and
1095 cosmetics (Gao et al., 2023). It is worth noting that in order to inhibit the release of MPs into
1096 water, many countries have banned the use of synthetic polymer microparticles, and thus the use
1097 of glitter and other MPs in cosmetics (see Table 2), which will contribute to reducing their transfer
1098 from wastewater to sludge. Nevertheless, the presence of these particles in wastewater, sludge
1099 and the environment may indicate their accumulation and circulation in the environment before
1100 the regulations were introduced.

1101 The microplastic content in sewage sludge has been found to depend very closely on their
1102 concentration in raw wastewater (see Table S3) with the amount of MPs extracted from the
1103 sludge ranging from 4196 to 15 385 MPs/g d.m. (dry matter) (Y. Hu et al., 2019). In a study
1104 involving three WWTPs with different configurations, the concentration of MPs in sludge ranged
1105 from approximately 36.0 MPs/g d.m. dry sludge in the activated sludge plant without pre-
1106 clarification to 81.1 MPs/g d.m. in the membrane bioreactor installation (di Bella et al., 2022). It
1107 can be seen that subsequent sludge management is a crucial step to avoid the release of MPs into
1108 the environment (Menéndez-Manjón et al., 2022). In general, the number of MPs in sludge
1109 increases during the technological process. The mean content ranges from 1.67 to 5.8 MPs/g d.m.
1110 in primary sludge (J. Jiang et al., 2020; Pittura et al., 2021), compared to 5.3 to 133 MPs/g d.m. in
1111 secondary sludge (di Bella et al., 2022; Edo et al., 2020; J. Jiang et al., 2020; Pittura et al., 2021;
1112 Tadsuwan & Babel, 2021; Uddin et al., 2022), although levels as high as 1919.74 MPs/g d.m. have
1113 also been reported (Cunsolo et al., 2021).

1114 Sewage sludge can be landfilled, incinerated or used for agricultural purposes (Lofty et al.,
1115 2022; Rolsky et al., 2020), although the final disposal method of varies from country to country
1116 and depends on local legislation. Due to its high organic and nutrient content, in many countries,
1117 the main recycling and reuse methods are land/agricultural use of sludge (e.g. Norway 82%,
1118 Ireland 63%, USA 55%, China 45%, Sweden 36%) and incineration (e.g. Netherlands 99%, Korea
1119 55%, Canada 47%) (W. Liu et al., 2021). To enable more cost-effective sludge management, it is

1120 necessary to reduce the volume sewage sludge by removing excess water (Obermaier & Pistocchi,
1121 2022). Due to its high organic and nutrient content, the main approach to recycling sewage sludge
1122 is to use it as a soil improver or fertilizer (Mabrouk et al., 2023; Rolsky et al., 2020; Uddin et al.,
1123 2022). In order to reduce the volume of the sludge and prepare it for possible further treatment,
1124 it is thickened and dewatered, which may result in the release of some MPs into the seep water,
1125 which returns to the system (Mabrouk et al., 2023). The type of MPs present in the sludge may
1126 also be influenced by further treatment, such as lime stabilization, anaerobic digestion, and
1127 thermal drying. For example, lime-stabilized sludge has been found to contain higher numbers of
1128 small MPs, probably as a result of the hydrolysis and melting of particles under high pH and
1129 temperature conditions (Gao et al., 2023). The retention of MPs in WWTP sludge affects
1130 anaerobic digestion parameters such as organic matter dissolution, volatile fatty acid production
1131 and microbiological performance (Kong et al., 2023). It is estimated that 63,000 to 430,000 tons
1132 of microplastics are added to European crops annually along with sewage sludge (Piehl et al.,
1133 2018).

1134 Understanding the fate of MPs in sludge management and their potential morphological
1135 changes, degradation, comminution and subsequent release to the environment requires further
1136 research (Habib et al., 2020; Rolsky et al., 2020). Land use by improperly-treated sludge raises
1137 increasing concerns about the transfer of toxic substances to the environment, such as heavy
1138 metals, which can be adsorbed to MPs (Medyńska-Juraszek & Jadhav, 2022).

1139 **5.6. Soil**

1140 The soil ecosystem is exposed to a wide range of MNPs due to the excessive exploitation
1141 and disorganized management of plastic waste. Microplastics typically enter soil through littering,
1142 atmospheric deposition and surface runoff from streets, with a significant proportion being worn
1143 tire fragments; in addition, high MPs levels in soil have been associated with improper disposal
1144 of municipal waste, the use of sewage sludge as fertilizers on farms or the use of plastic mulch
1145 (mulching film) during planting crops (Y. R. Choi et al., 2021; Iqbal et al., 2021).

1146 MPs found in soil come in various sizes. Although meso- and macroplastics occur as
1147 a result of littering, e.g. forests, the most common are smaller particles, which are the result of
1148 long-term fragmentation in soil and deposition of plastic waste in the topsoil (Y. R. Choi et al.,
1149 2021). The horizontal distribution of MPs in the soil is influenced by agricultural practices,
1150 including plowing, and harvesting. The vertical distribution depends on soil fracturing and soil
1151 macropores, which allow MPs to penetrate deeper into the soil profile (Pandey et al., 2022).

1152 Mulch films have been widely used in agriculture for several decades (Khalid et al., 2023),
1153 for example in vegetable plantations, including rice, lettuce and broccoli, or fruit trees and flowers
1154 (Beriot et al., 2021; van Schothorst et al., 2021). The most common types of polymers in
1155 agricultural soil samples are PE, followed by PP and PS (Piehl et al., 2018). PE films are most often
1156 used for mulching (Y. R. Choi et al., 2021). This was also confirmed by studies conducted in

1157 Western Germany (Steinmetz & Schröder, 2022), which found the PE content to be significantly
1158 higher in fields mulched with plastic than in the reference fields. In turn, other types of soils often
1159 exhibit PES and PA fibers or small fragments of black styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) associated
1160 with tire dust, in addition to PE, PP and PS, PVC, PMMA and acrylates (Y. R. Choi et al., 2021).
1161 Using plastic mulch offers greater ease of installation and resistance to weather conditions, as
1162 well as higher yields and lower water and pesticide consumption (Steinmetz & Schröder, 2022);
1163 it also helps maintain soil moisture and regulate soil temperature. However, these films are also
1164 brittle, which means that their fragments can remain in the soil at the end of the growing season
1165 and penetrate deeper layers of the soil during subsequent cropping (Khalid et al., 2023; Steinmetz
1166 & Schröder, 2022). It is therefore advantageous to implement appropriate methods for the
1167 disposal or recycling of this mulch film or to use alternative materials such as paper or straw
1168 mulching or photodegradable or biodegradable plastic mulch film (Khalid et al., 2023).

1169 The form and distribution of MPs soil contamination varies according to the location of
1170 road traffic and both current and previous agriculture and land use (Medyńska-Juraszek &
1171 Szczepańska, 2023). For example, in the city of Yeju in South Korea, six times more small
1172 microplastics (<1 mm) were detected near streets than large microplastics (5-1 mm) associated
1173 with agricultural activities (Y. R. Choi et al., 2021). Medyńska-Juraszek and Szczepańska reported
1174 that 93% of arable soils in southwestern Poland contained MPs (Medyńska-Juraszek &
1175 Szczepańska, 2023). In sandy soils, 383 ± 188 MPs/kg soil were detected, compared to 1540 ± 912
1176 MPs/kg in loamy soils and 933 ± 682 MPs/kg in clay soils. This suggests that microplastics are less
1177 susceptible to leaching in compact soils with high clay mineral and organic matter content.
1178 Interestingly, compost from organic waste and green clippings was found to contain
1179 microplastics, which can be transferred to arable land when used as their use as fertilizer (Huerta-
1180 Lwanga et al., 2022). Indeed, substantial amounts of MPs particles (up to 4050 ± 2831 MPs/kg)
1181 were detected in soils fertilized with sewage sludge, sewage and green waste composts
1182 (Medyńska-Juraszek & Szczepańska, 2023).

1183 The contamination of soil with MPs can cause serious environmental problems and
1184 potentially threaten soil ecosystems and human health (M. Zhang et al., 2022). The presence of
1185 MPs in soil can cause many physical, chemical, and biological changes. MPs can disrupt the
1186 ecological stability of biogeochemical cycles and influence soil pH or the levels of nutrients, such
1187 as organic carbon, organic phosphorus, phosphate, organic nitrogen, and ammonium nitrogen)
1188 (Chia et al., 2021; M. Zhang et al., 2022). Physical changes include changes in aggregate stability,
1189 soil bulk/density, and water dynamics (Chia et al., 2021). As microplastics migrate into the soil, its
1190 structure and function change, as does microbial diversity (Pandey et al., 2022). Biological
1191 changes, in turn, may include, among others, activity of soil microbes and fauna (Riveros et al.,
1192 2022; M. Zhang et al., 2022). Soil fauna such as earthworms, soil larvae and vertebrates ingest
1193 MPs and facilitate their transport in the soil profile during their digestion (Huerta-Lwanga et al.,
1194 2022). Additionally, soil enzyme variability and litter decomposition can affect the

1195 biogeochemistry of nutrients and organic matter. Therefore, changes in the structure and activity
1196 of microbial communities are inevitable (Iqbal et al., 2021). Moreover, negative impacts on plants
1197 and animals, as well as threats to food quality and safety, have been observed (Pandey et al.,
1198 2022).

1199 The use of MPs may have positive aspects, e.g. the use of PE foam in floriculture promotes
1200 soil respiration and increases soil pore space, water and air flow, thus increasing soil microbial
1201 activity (T. Zhao et al., 2021) or increasing soil macroporosity and facilitating root penetration,
1202 improving plant growth (Lozano & Rillig, 2022). However, they generally have an overall negative
1203 impact on soil physical properties, plant health and soil degradation. The consumption of
1204 microplastics through drinking water from groundwater can be harmful to human health. Soil
1205 microplastics can also exert pressure on the growth of plants and soil organisms, and can lead to
1206 the death of soil organisms (Chia et al., 2021).

1207 Plastic pollution is considered to be a major factor in the global decline in biodiversity. This
1208 poses a threat to soil system functioning and has been documented in ecosystems worldwide
1209 (Barnes et al. 2009; Qi et al. 2020).

1210 **5.7. Biota**

1211 Human activity has been closely linked with the decline or disappearance of various species and
1212 is recognized as a factor significantly threatening global biodiversity. Mitigating such loss poses
1213 a major challenge within the context of the so-called triple planetary crisis (UNEP, 2022a). The
1214 causes of biodiversity loss are varied and include overfishing, habitat destruction, such as
1215 deforestation for development, and desertification driven by climate change. Furthermore,
1216 through the transformation, migration, and transmission of pollutants such as MPs and NPs, and
1217 facilitating their trophic transfer, human activity presents an additional threat to trophic networks
1218 (Maddela et al., 2023). Such changes can affect the physicochemical properties of the soil, soil
1219 microflora, invertebrates, and plant systems, with the result depending on the composition of the
1220 polymers, added substances, and duration of exposure.

1221 **5.7.1. Microorganisms**

1222 The widespread presence of MPs in the environment has led to the emergence of studies
1223 on the interaction between MPs and microorganisms, with some examining the diversity and
1224 characteristics of those that can form fully-fledged biofilms on substrates (Qiu et al., 2022). MPs
1225 provide a suitable surface for microbial adhesion and biofilm formation, and thus the attachment
1226 and adsorption of many other contaminants and pathogenic microorganisms; as such, they may
1227 also become a transfer point for antimicrobial resistance genes (Kutralam-Muniasamy et al.,
1228 2024; Nath et al., 2023). This biofilm formed by the bacteria, fungi, viruses, archaea, algae and
1229 protozoa that colonize the surface of microplastics has been called the *plastisphere* (Bao et al.,
1230 2022; Zhai et al., 2023). Aquatic and terrestrial plastispheres are formed in a similar manner, with

1231 the plastic particles being occupied by microorganisms known as opportunistic microorganisms
1232 or hitchhikers (K. H. D. Tang, 2024).

1233 Research is ongoing into the composition of the plastisphere for both salt and fresh waters and
1234 the role of the plastisphere in the chemical biotransformation and physical modification of plastic
1235 debris. However, these are not simple analyses, mainly due to the lack of standardization of
1236 sampling methods and their analysis.

1237 The composition of the microbial community and dominant species in the plastisphere
1238 differs significantly from than of the surrounding environments, whether in freshwater and
1239 saltwater or other matrices, as they differ with age, plastic properties, and biotic and abiotic
1240 environmental factors (K. H. D. Tang, 2024; Zhai et al., 2023). Previous research has not shown
1241 that any microorganisms occur only on plastic particles (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2020). The
1242 interactions between microbes and MPs depend on environmental factors, such as the
1243 temperature and pH of the microenvironment and ionic strength, as well as on the surface
1244 properties of MPs, including their size, shape, roughness, and hydrophobicity (Yang et al., 2023).
1245 Interactions with external factors are mainly driven by hydrophobicity and electrostatic forces.

1246 The microorganisms in the plastisphere are often defined by the dominant
1247 microorganisms in a given environment. In the plastisphere, the early dominant pioneer
1248 communities consist of primary producers, including diatoms, cyanobacteria, green algae, and
1249 bacteria (Zhai et al., 2023). Among these, bacteria from the phyla *Proteobacteria*, *Actinobacteria*,
1250 *Bacteroidota*, *Firmicutes*, *Chloroflexi*, *Acidobacteria* and *Cyanobacteria*, and fungi from the phyla
1251 *Ascomycota*, *Basidiomycota*, and *Chytridiomycota* are commonly mentioned (K. H. D. Tang, 2024).

1252 Research indicates that plastispheres can act as a vector of transimssion of various viruses,
1253 including *Myoviridae*, *Podoviridae*, *Siphoviridae*, *Pycodnaviridae*, *Mimiviridae* and *Caudovirales*
1254 (Kutralam-Muniasamy et al., 2024). This suggest that organisms inhabiting plastispheres can be
1255 transferred in the trophic pyramid, potentially leading to toxic effects (Bao et al., 2022). It should
1256 be remembered that even in the absence of living microorganisms, microbiological components
1257 released from deceased bacteria can bind to the surfaces of MPs (Yang et al., 2023). While the
1258 transfer of MPs and the various contaminants adsorbed on them are known to occur, their
1259 influence on human health and food safety remain unclear (Amaral-Zettler et al., 2020).

1260 **5.7.2. Plants**

1261 Plants are fundamental living elements of terrestrial ecosystems and are a vital source of
1262 food for humans. Given the crucial role of agricultural ecosystems in food production and their
1263 close connection with soil biodiversity, the presence of MPs in the terrestrial environment creates
1264 numerous potential pathways for exposure to MPs for both humans and other living organisms,
1265 which could harm both ecosystem health and human wellbeing (Rochman, 2018). Thus,
1266 understanding the dynamics of interactions between MPs and plants, especially those intended
1267 for human consumption, is key to assessing the risks associated with microplastic pollution.

1268 The use of wastewater to irrigate agricultural crops worldwide raises the question of MNPs
1269 absorption by plants. The surface properties of MNPs, such as hydrophobicity and higher surface-
1270 to-volume ratios, enhance their capacity to adsorb and carry various pollutants. MPs and NPs can
1271 enter plants via two main routes: absorption through the roots and direct deposition on leaves.
1272 This adsorption capacity can be further increased by converting hydrophobic MPs into hydrophilic
1273 ones using surfactants (S. Xia et al., 2020). The hydrophobic nature of MPs and NPs facilitates
1274 their role as vectors for contaminants like antibiotics, pesticides, and heavy metals (Rillig et al.,
1275 2019; Wan et al., 2019). Nanoparticles smaller than 50 nm can penetrate cell membranes and
1276 absorb pathogenic microbes, increasing the biohazard potential of both the plastics and the
1277 pathogens involved. Aging and degradation of MNPs in the environment can influence the
1278 ecocorona, potentially resulting in varying levels of toxicity to soil and crops (Nasser & Lynch,
1279 2016).

1280 Furthermore, MNPs can inhibit plant growth. Exposing plants to MNPs disrupts their
1281 physiological and biochemical balance, resulting in changes to their metabolism (L. Li et al., 2020).
1282 This contamination triggers oxidative stress, leading to increased reactive oxygen species (ROS)
1283 production in plant tissues and cell damage (Pehlivan & Gedik, 2021). To counteract this, plants
1284 activate their antioxidant systems, producing both enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants,
1285 such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), peroxidase (POD), and ascorbate peroxidase
1286 (APX) (Judy et al., 2019). However, polymers like PS, PE, PP, PVC, and PTEF disrupt the production
1287 of these critical enzymes, leading to tissue death and reduced crop yield (S. Liu et al., 2021;
1288 Pehlivan & Gedik, 2021; Santamaría et al., 2018; Wu et al., 2021).

1289 While MPs are generally too large to pass through the physical defenses of intact plant
1290 tissue (L. Li et al., 2020), they can readily adhere to the surface of plant roots and seeds (Bosker
1291 et al., 2019; X. Jiang et al., 2019). Moreover, although these particles are unable to penetrate cell
1292 walls, they can obstruct the pores or junctions between cells, thus impeding the flow of water
1293 and nutrients into plant cells. In contrast, being smaller, ranging from 1 nm to 1 μ m, NPs are
1294 capable of penetrating plant cell walls. These NPs can enter root tips via the epidermis or
1295 rhizodermis, and follow pathways between cell walls, particularly through routes involving
1296 lignified epidermis (S. Zhang et al., 2019). As a result, the roots and other organs involved in
1297 nutrient uptake in vascular plants are particularly susceptible to nanoparticle absorption (H. Sun
1298 et al., 2021). Once inside, the nanoparticles are transported to the endodermis through osmotic
1299 pressure and capillary action, in a process known as the apoplastic pathway (Roy et al., 2023).

1300 Additionally, NPs are also able to penetrate at the sites where lateral roots form. Instances
1301 of PS microbead absorption in wheat and lettuce have been noted from the emergence point of
1302 lateral roots to the stele, utilizing the crack-entry pathway (L. Li et al., 2020). Both PMMA and PS
1303 nanoparticles were found to be taken up from the apex of the root and then traverse through the
1304 epidermal layers in regions lacking a fully-developed Casparian strip. As a result, PS nanoparticles
1305 moved through the apoplastic spaces to reach the xylem vessels, facilitating their transport from

1306 the root system to the aerial parts of the plant (L. Li et al., 2020). Confocal microscopy images
1307 revealed the entry of PS beads, both in submicrometre (0.2 μm) and micrometre-sized (2.0 μm)
1308 dimensions, into the xylem vessels at sites where lateral roots of wheat emerge. However, the
1309 larger 2.0 μm PS beads were unable to penetrate the epidermis or cortex at the root tip.

1310 Additionally, NPs might utilize a straightforward pathway for interaction with membrane
1311 proteins, ion channels, and aquaporins, participating in the processes of ion transport and cellular
1312 uptake through endocytosis (Tripathi et al., 2017). Regarding the mechanism of endocytosis, it
1313 was observed in one investigation that NPs (specifically PS beads) were able to infiltrate tobacco
1314 plant cells through a form of endocytosis that does not involve clathrin (Bandmann et al., 2012).
1315 Moreover, a recent study identified that the roots of rice plants are capable of ingesting PS-based
1316 NPs (100 nm in size) through endocytotic processes (Wu et al., 2021). Consequently, after
1317 penetrating the root system, NPs can move to different plant parts, with the extent of this
1318 movement being influenced by the transpiration stream (Dong et al., 2020; L. Li et al., 2020; Roy
1319 et al., 2023).

1320 Microplastic particles can also be absorbed through the leaves, i.e. by the stomatal
1321 pathway. Nanoparticles can penetrate through the stomata and be transported to various plant
1322 areas via apoplastic pathways (J. Zhao et al., 2017). This was similarly highlighted in a recent study
1323 on lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.) subjected to foliar exposure to PS-based nanoparticles for varying
1324 durations. Microscopic analysis revealed that PS-NPs entered the leaves through the stomata and
1325 moved towards the roots through the vascular bundle (Lv et al., 2019). Additional analysis of the
1326 leaf surface showed a considerable buildup of PS-based NPs around the stomata. Other studies
1327 (Luo et al., 2022) found that PS particles (0.2 μm) accumulated in, or had a significant presence
1328 within, the xylem and cortex tissues of both the roots and leaves of lettuce and wheat.

1329 Generally, these findings suggest that once NPs the vascular bundle of the roots, they can
1330 navigate along the vascular cylinder, utilizing the xylem pathways to transport water and
1331 nutrients to the shoots and leaves. In addition, the entry of nanoparticles through leaf stomata
1332 indicates that these tiny particles can also move through another transport mechanism, namely
1333 the phloem, which is crucial for the distribution of sugars and amino acids from the leaves to
1334 other plant parts.

1335 These points highlight the complex and multifaceted impacts of MPs and NPs on plant
1336 health and soil ecosystems, emphasizing the need for further research into their ecological and
1337 agricultural implications.

1338 **5.7.3. Animals**

1339 It is estimated that plastics currently threaten the survival of more than 800 animal species
1340 (Kudzin et al., 2023). Nowadays, it is often observed that animals use plastic as a material for
1341 building nests or shelters (Blettler & Mitchell, 2021). The phenomenon of plastic waste ingestion
1342 has been demonstrated in both large and small food webs among hundreds of species of wild

1343 animals, particularly marine animals (Provencher et al., 2019) (Table S4). Among seabirds,
1344 particularly large amounts of plastic are ingested by albatrosses and petrels, which swallow it
1345 along with their prey. Petrels, due to their intestinal morphology, retain plastic in their bodies for
1346 a longer period of time, which makes them particularly vulnerable to its adverse effects (Clark et
1347 al., 2023), such as blockage of the digestive system (Shaji et al., 2023). In addition, plastic waste
1348 can be washed ashore and suspended in the water column; this waste can pose a threat to
1349 seabirds, fish, turtles and mammals by entangling them (Bergmann et al., 2015), leading to
1350 lacerations, infections and starvation (Shaji et al., 2023).

1351 MPs exposure has been found to result in decreased body weight, increased oxidative
1352 stress and even death (Büks et al., 2020). Laboratory studies conducted on mice found that long-
1353 term oral exposure to low (0.0025 mg/ml), medium (0.025 mg/ml) and high doses to MPs
1354 (0.125 mg/ml) can lead to behavioral changes, as well as changes in immune markers, and liver
1355 and brain tissue. Moreover, treatment with 0.1 and 2 μm PS-MPs at concentrations ranging from
1356 0.01 to 1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ was found to decrease the viability of U-2 OS cell lines after 48 and 72 hours,
1357 with the effect increasing with MPs concentrations (Gaspar et al., 2023).

1358 Exposure to MPs concentrations corresponding to those occurring in the environment
1359 (0.008 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$, 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$ and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) resulted in an increase in hemolymph acid phosphatase
1360 activity in *Mytilus spp.* (mussel) with 10-day toxicological analyses revealing disorders in
1361 antioxidant enzymes (Revel et al., 2019). Also in the marine copepod *Tigriopus japonicus*,
1362 exposure to PS of 50 nm and 10 μm resulted in changes in the levels of antioxidant enzymes and
1363 transcription disorders of genes related to ROS expression (J. S. Choi et al., 2020); exposure has
1364 also been associated with decreased fertility (J. Sun et al., 2021)

1365 Exposure to PVC microparticles inhibited the growth of the microalga *Skeletonema*
1366 *costatum*. A maximum growth inhibition ratio (IR) of 39.7% was achieved after 96-hour exposure.
1367 Moreover, at a high PVC concentration (50 mg/L), lower chlorophyll content and photosynthetic
1368 efficiency was observed (C. Zhang et al., 2017).

1369 It should also be noted that ingestion of MPs by animals can also cause physical injuries to
1370 the body such as an inflammatory response, inhibition of gastric enzyme secretion, or
1371 gastrointestinal obstruction (Fu et al., 2020). Studies conducted on zebrafish showed that PE at a
1372 concentration of 2 mg/L and a size between 19.7 and 558.4 μm , occupied 89% of the intestinal
1373 surface.

1374 This resulted in a reduced amount of space for food. In addition, increased expression of
1375 *cyp1* genes in the intestine, as well as *vtg1* in the liver caused by exposure to microplastics, led to
1376 behavioral changes including convulsions and tail bending (Mak et al., 2019).

1377 The level of absorption, elimination time from the body and toxicity depend on various factors,
1378 such as age, sex, genotype, trophic level, feeding habits and foraging behaviour (Saad & Alamin,
1379 2024; Toussaint et al., 2019).

1380

5.7.4. Humans

1381 Exposure to MPs and NPs has a considerable impact on human health. The main routes of
1382 MNPs uptake include ingestion and inhalation (Revel et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2023). Airborne
1383 MPs/NPs, often originating from synthetic textiles, rubber tires, and dust, are primarily inhaled
1384 (Prata, 2018; Prata, Da Costa, et al., 2020); however, Lehner et al. emphasize that ingestion is the
1385 predominant route by which humans encounter MNPs, leading to various health effects (Lehner
1386 et al., 2019).

1387 It is estimated that each individual ingests between 39,000 and 52,000 microplastic
1388 particles each year, varying by age, sex, and occupation. This number increases to 74,000 –
1389 121,000 particles when inhalation is also included (Cox et al., 2019). Many of our primary food
1390 sources, including cereals, pulses, oilseed crops, vegetables, and fruits can all be contaminated
1391 with MNPs. However, the effects of these particles on the human body after consumption remain
1392 poorly understood. As such, the potential of microplastics to induce cancer and their cumulative,
1393 non-specific long-term health implications require further research.

1394 Generally, after the ingestion of MNPs, potential translocation and subsequent absorption
1395 can occur through the digestive system. Research suggests that microplastics larger than 150 μm
1396 are unlikely to be absorbed, while those MPs under 150 μm might move from the gut into the
1397 lymphatic and circulatory systems, leading to limited systemic exposure. It is believed that only
1398 microplastics smaller than 20 μm can enter organs, and only the smallest particles (between 0.1
1399 and 10 μm) have the potential to reach all body organs, cross cell membranes, and penetrate the
1400 blood-brain barrier and placenta (Barboza, 2018; EFSA, 2016; Kirstein, 2021). This could result in
1401 the spread of microplastics to secondary tissues, such as the liver, muscles and brain (Wright &
1402 Kelly, 2017). In addition, *in vitro* research on human cerebral and epithelial cells has shown that
1403 microplastics (10 μm) and nanoplastics (40–250 nm) possess cytotoxic capabilities, especially
1404 associated with oxidative stress (Schirinzi et al., 2017). Furthermore, interactions between micro-
1405 and nanoplastics and the immune system might result in immunotoxic effects, leading to
1406 potential adverse health impacts such as immunosuppression, activation of the immune system,
1407 and atypical inflammatory reactions (Wright & Kelly, 2017).

1408 Plastic particle polymers such as PS, PP, and PET also have been detected and quantified
1409 in human blood (Leslie et al., 2022). Moreover, laboratory research indicates that PS particles,
1410 measuring 202 and 535 nanometers, can trigger inflammation in human lung cells (M. Hu & Palić,
1411 2020). Ye et al. (Ye et al., 2010) found that the accumulation of nanoparticles in the bloodstream
1412 and heart tissue could impede blood circulation and potentially cause heart disease. Additionally,
1413 Lu et al. (Lu et al., 2016) report that the accumulation of microplastics and nanoplastics in the
1414 digestive and hepatic systems might lead to inflammation, lipid accumulation in the liver, and
1415 oxidative stress, marked by elevated levels of *inter alia* catalase and superoxide dismutase.

1416 Prata et al. (Prata, Da Costa, et al., 2020) report that microplastics and nanoplastics can
1417 increase the risk of oxidative stress and cytotoxicity, which could increase the chances of chronic

1418 inflammation and cancer. These particles may also negatively impact the gut diversity and
1419 function of the microbiome, potentially leading to obesity, diabetes, and chronic liver disease
1420 (Meier et al., 2022; Weiss & Hennet, n.d.). Studies also indicate that microplastics and
1421 nanoplastics can affect the stability of the gut, male fertility, and the health of future generations
1422 (O'Neill & Lawler, 2021). Additionally, compounds known to bind to microplastics and
1423 nanoplastics, such as phthalates and BPA, are linked to reproductive health problems,
1424 cardiovascular conditions, hormonal imbalances, obesity, cancer, and birth defects (Gómez &
1425 Gallart-Ayala, 2018; Koelmans, 2014). Additionally, research has indicated that PS beads (50, 80,
1426 and 240 nm) and micro-sized PP can cross the human placental barrier (Ragusa, 2021; Wick et al.,
1427 2010). Exposure to 44 nm PS-NPs has been reported to reduce cell viability, modify gene
1428 expression, and induce cellular and inflammatory abnormalities (Nadanaciva et al., 2011).

1429 To summarize, both microplastics and nanoplastics cause a range of health concerns and
1430 are associated with prolonged health risks. There is hence an urgent need for comprehensive
1431 dose-response modeling of microplastics to enhance our understanding of their effects.
1432 Additionally, MPs and NPs may also be vectors for disease, and comprehensive human studies
1433 are needed to address these pressing health concerns.

1434 **6. Regulations**

1435 As MPs and NPs have been found in all environmental matrices and organisms at various
1436 levels of the trophic pyramid (see Figure 5), there is a need to institute legal regulations regarding
1437 the number of plastics introduced into the environment.

1438 Despite the wealth of reports on the potential health effects on living organisms, there are
1439 currently no legal regulations regulating the amounts of plastic particles in drinking water or
1440 treated wastewater introduced into waters and soil. There is a great need to standardize suitable
1441 sampling and analytical protocols and design advanced technologies that can improve their
1442 removal.

1443 Some regulations restrict the introduction and use of plastic microbeads or bisphenol-A in
1444 drinking water (see Table 2). In addition, the constantly growing number of scientific publications
1445 on MPs and NPs do not share a uniform methodology or analysis, which makes it difficult to
1446 compare results. Even despite the publication of ISO 24187:2023(E): Principles for the analysis of
1447 microplastics present in the environment (ISO, 2023), as mentioned in Section 4, the document
1448 contains only general guidelines for the collection, preparation and analysis of samples containing
1449 MPs from various matrices.

1450 The following section presents current selected legal acts or recommendations regarding
1451 industrial production, plastic waste management as well as methodology and analysis of plastic
1452 particles in environmental samples.

1453 **6.1. Industrial production and the content of plastic particles in products**

1454 The first reports on the harmfulness of plastics to human health concerned Bisphenol-A
1455 (BPA). BPA is a hardener used in industry since the 1950s to produce various polymers, mainly PC
1456 plastics. It has been shown to be an endocrine disruptor that, even in small doses, can lead to
1457 breast and prostate cancer, obesity, neurobehavioral problems, and reproductive abnormalities
1458 (Vogel, 2009). The use of Bisphenol-A (BPA) has been restricted in many consumer products,
1459 including materials that come into contact with food, and toys. For example, the European Union
1460 banned the use of BPA in the production of baby feeding bottles and similar products (European
1461 Parliament, 2009), or Canada's Government in Consumer Product Safety Act (Government of
1462 Canada, 2010).

1463 In 2015, the United States passed federal legislation banning the use of polymer
1464 microbeads in cosmetics that are flushed down the drain due to their harmful effects on the
1465 environment (US Congress, 2015). The definition of *microbeads* is consistent with the National
1466 Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's definition of *microplastic* (Mausra & Foster, 2015),
1467 which states that microbeads are most commonly used in personal care products, such as
1468 exfoliants in facial scrubs. In contrast, the US government's restriction uses a broad definition of
1469 microplastic: it includes all synthetic polymer particles less than 5 mm in diameter that are
1470 organic, insoluble, and resistant to degradation (US Congress, 2015). Similar restrictions on the
1471 use of microbeads have also been adopted by other countries, including Canada (Government of
1472 Canada, 2017), the European Union (European Parliament, 2023a), China (NDRC, 2020), New
1473 Zealand (New Zealand's Government, 2022), and Thailand (Thailand's Ministry of Public Health,
1474 2019).

1475 Moreover, to ensure public health, regulations have been prepared to regulate plastic
1476 packaging materials in contact with food. An example is the European Commission Regulation No.
1477 10/2011 (European Parliament, 2011), whose aim is to ensure that substances present in newly-
1478 produced plastic do not enter food in quantities that may harm human health. In 2022,
1479 regulations were issued for recycled plastics in contact with food (European Parliament, 2022a).
1480 Additionally, in 2019, the European Commission issued Directive No. 2019/904 on reducing
1481 single-use plastic waste that has a negative impact on the environment (European Parliament,
1482 2019). Similar regulations for packaging in contact with food or for cosmetic substances have
1483 been introduced in other countries, e.g. in China (PRC, 2016, 2021). Another example is the Single-
1484 Use Plastics Reduction Campaign Pledge proposed by the United Kingdom National Health Service
1485 (NHS) to reduce the use of single-use plastics in the healthcare system (NHS England, 2019) or the
1486 Environmental Protection Regulations of May 2020 regarding the use of plastic materials such as
1487 plastic straws, cotton buds and stirrers (UK Parliament, 2020).

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1490 **Table 2.** Legal regulations regarding microplastics in various countries of the world and the European
 1491 Union

Topic	Country	Title	Reference
Microbeads in cosmetics	United States	Microbead-Free Waters Act (H.R.1321 - 114th Congress (2015-2016))	(US Congress, 2015)
	Canada	Microbeads in Toiletries Regulations	(Government of Canada, 2017)
	European Union	Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055 of 25 September 2023 amending Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) as regards synthetic polymer microparticles	(European Parliament, 2023a)
	China	Refined Standards for Relevant Plastic Products Bans and Limits Management (2020 Edition) - Development, Reform and Environmental Protection Regulations [2020] No. 1146.	(NDRC, 2020)
	New Zealand	Waste Minimisation (Plastic and Related Products) Amendment Regulations 2022	(New Zealand's Government, 2022)
	Thailand	Announcement of the Ministry of Public Health on specifying the characteristics of cosmetics that are prohibited from being produced, imported, or sold (No. 2)	(Thailand's Ministry of Public Health, 2019)
Bisphenol-A	European Union	Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/213 of 12 February 2018 on the Use of Bisphenol A in Varnishes and Coatings Intended to Come into Contact with Food and Amending Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 as Regards the Use of That Substance in Plastic Food Contact Materials, (OJ L 041/61)	(European Parliament, 2018)
	Canada	Canada Consumer Product Safety Act (S.C. 2010, c. 21)	(Government of Canada, 2010)

1492 **6.2. Methods of analysis and detection of plastic particles in the environment**

1493 There are currently no uniform guidelines for the collection and preparation of
 1494 environmental samples for microplastic analysis. The latest regulations (September 2023) issued
 1495 by the International Standard Organization contain only some recommendations for the use of
 1496 best practices in sampling for MPs analysis and for environmental sampling (ISO, 2023). Other
 1497 protocols the have been used in research for the analysis of plastic particles in various matrices
 1498 are listed in Section 4.

1499 In addition, it should be noted that many countries are striving to establish common
 1500 uniform regulations for the collection and analysis of samples, and to establish a limit for plastic
 1501 particles in the environment. For example, in March 2024, the European Commission issued
 1502 a report entitled *Analytical methods to measure microplastics in drinking water* (European
 1503 Commission JRC, 2024). The information collected in this report presents the state of the scientific
 1504 base on the nature, distribution, and amount of microplastics in drinking water, and additionally

1505 indicates potential instrumental techniques for the methodology of monitoring and analysis of
1506 MPs in drinking water.

1507 It is also planned to create a ‘watchlist’ of health components of drinking water that are
1508 of concern to citizens and scientists (WHO Europe, 2017). This includes microplastics,
1509 pharmaceuticals and endocrine disruptors.

1510 **6.3. MNPs content in environmental matrices, recycling and circular economy**

1511 The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2021) lists only a few established and
1512 internationally-recognized standards and certification systems referring to the biodegradability,
1513 recycling and degradation of plastics during industrial composting and in the marine environment,
1514 e.g. ISO 15279, ISO/CD 22722 and ISO 18830. It emphasizes that efforts should also be made to
1515 develop clear standards for labeling products as biodegradable to help reduce the risk of plastic
1516 pollution and related hazards in the marine environment.

1517 In response to these calls, some regulations have begun to be developed, with the aim of
1518 achieving a ‘zero plastic waste strategy’ by 2030 or 2060. For example, in April 2023, the
1519 Government of Canada published a regulatory framework paper on recycled content, labelling
1520 rules and registry for plastics titled *Recycled content and labelling rules for plastics: Regulatory*
1521 *Framework Paper* (Government of Canada, 2023). In November 2022, the European Union issued
1522 a communication on an EU policy framework for bio-based, biodegradable and compostable
1523 plastics (European Parliament, 2022b). While the communication is not legally binding, it provides
1524 insight into the likely future direction of EU legislation regarding alternatives to traditional
1525 plastics. Additionally, in March 2023, a *Proposal for a Directive on Green Claims* was issued
1526 (European Parliament, 2023b).

1527 In 2016, the UNEP and the Ellen MacArthur Foundation launched a global commitment
1528 called the *New Plastics Economy*, the main goal of which is to unite businesses, governments and
1529 other organizations around a shared vision of a circular economy for plastics (World Economic
1530 Forum et al., 2016). The UNEP strategy is to return plastics to the economy as valuable technical
1531 or biological nutrients, thus never becoming waste or pollution. The new plastics economy is
1532 based on the principles of the circular economy (UNEP, 2022b). Such a transition requires
1533 a whole-system approach by creating an effective post-use management of plastics, drastically
1534 reducing the transfer of plastics to natural ecosystems (especially the ocean) and other negative
1535 externalities (World Economic Forum et al., 2016).

1536 Achieving the global goal of eliminating plastic pollution, as presented in the New Plastics
1537 Economy, requires commitment at both the regional and international levels (OECD, 2022). This
1538 means preparing and implementing policies by 2060 to improve waste management and
1539 recycling, reduce demand for plastics, or extend the life of products through reuse. Countries
1540 should strive for a circular economy and aim to close loops, while supporting non-OECD countries

1541 (OECD - *Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development*) in their efforts to improve
1542 *inter alia* waste management.

1543 **7. Conclusions**

1544 Plastic pollution exacerbates the planetary crisis and causes extensive damage to ecosystems and
1545 human health; as such it stands as one of the greatest environmental challenges of the 21st
1546 century (OECD, 2022; UNEP, 2022b). Despite the integral role of plastic materials in the global
1547 economy and their ubiquitous presence across all economic sectors, there is an urgent need to
1548 increase awareness about plastic consumption and management, and to emphasize the reuse of
1549 raw materials. This review provides a comprehensive examination of microplastics, and includes
1550 definitions, their presence in marine and food chains, detection methods, and risk evaluation. It
1551 establishes a critical baseline for future research on their effects on human and ecosystem health.
1552 Additionally, it highlights the importance of focusing future studies on the most harmful
1553 microplastics and prioritizing research efforts effectively through thorough risk assessment
1554 methods. Key findings and recommendations from this review include:

- 1555 • **Global production and persistence:** The scale of global plastic production and the
1556 persistence of plastic particles in the environment are alarming. This review offers
1557 a detailed analysis of the production, degradation, and classification of plastic debris,
1558 which is essential for understanding their long-term environmental presence.
- 1559 • **Analytical methodologies:** Advances in methodologies for preparing and analyzing
1560 environmental samples for plastic particle detection are crucial for accurately assessing
1561 contamination levels. The review outlines various techniques that enhance detection and
1562 analysis, thereby improving monitoring efforts.
- 1563 • **Impact on ecosystems:** Microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs) significantly affect
1564 various ecological components, from microorganisms and plants to animals and human
1565 health. The review details the complex interactions and disruptions caused by these
1566 particles within ecological systems.
- 1567 • **Environmental and health implications:** Long-term exposure to MPs and NPs poses
1568 serious health risks to living organisms, including humans. The review underscores the
1569 need for further research into the specific health impacts and toxicity mechanisms of
1570 these particles.
- 1571 • **Regulatory and policy frameworks:** Effective regulatory measures are urgently needed to
1572 control the production and release of plastic particles. The review discusses existing
1573 frameworks and proposes enhancements to better manage plastic pollution.
- 1574 • **Future research and innovation:** Identifying key factors influencing the transfer and
1575 transformation of plastic residues is essential. The review calls for innovative solutions
1576 and coordinated global research efforts to address knowledge gaps and develop strategies
1577 for mitigating the impact of MPs and NPs.

1578 In conclusion, this review highlights the critical need for a coordinated global response to manage
1579 micro(nano)plastic (MNPs) pollution. Enhanced environmental monitoring, effective regulatory
1580 frameworks, and innovative solutions are vital to mitigate the pervasive threat of plastic particles.
1581 Addressing these challenges is crucial for preserving ecosystem integrity, protecting biodiversity,
1582 and safeguarding human health from the detrimental effects of MNPs pollution.

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1590 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
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1592 **CRediT authorship contribution statement**

1593 K. Jaszczyszyn: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Visualization, E. Kiedrzyńska: Writing - review & editing,
1594 Supervision, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, D. Matuszewska: Visualization, Writing – review & editing, J.
1595 Xue: Writing – review & editing, M. Kiedrzyński: Writing – review & editing.

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